

MATERIAL SUPLEMENTARIO

Susceptibility analysis of mutations that confer resistance to inhibitors of the SARS-CoV-2 main protease (M^{pro}) and RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp)

Análisis de susceptibilidad a mutaciones que confieren resistencia a inhibidores de las enzimas proteasa principal (M^{pro}) y ARN polimerasa ARN-dependiente (RdRp) del SARS-CoV-2

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Tabla Suplementaria 1. Valores de similitud de secuencia entre M^{pro} y RdRp del SARS-CoV-2 y proteínas homólogas.

Nº	Código	Nombre de especie M ^{pro}	Valores de similitud
1.	P0C6F5	R1A_BC279 - Replicase polyprotein 1a Bat coronavirus 279/2005 (BtCoV) (BtCoV/279/2005)	E-value*: 0.0 Score †: 1604 Ident. ‡: 96.1%
2.	A0A0U1WHG8	A0A0U1WHG8_CVHSA - 2'-O-methyltransferase BtRf-BetaCoV/HeB2013	E-value: 0.0 Score: 1601 Ident.: 95.8%
3.	P0C6U8	R1A_CVHSA - Replicase polyprotein 1a Human SARS coronavirus (SARS-CoV) (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 1600 Ident.: 96.1%
4.	Q6UZF5	Q6UZF5_CVHSA - 2'-O-methyltransferase SARS coronavirus PUMC02	E-value: 0.0 Score: 1600 Ident.: 96.1%
5.	A0A0K1Z0N1	A0A0K1Z0N1_CVHSA - 3C-like proteinase Bat SARS-like coronavirus YNLF_31C	E-value: 0.0 Score: 1599 Ident.: 95.8%
6.	P0C6F8	R1A_BCHK3 - Replicase polyprotein 1a Bat coronavirus HKU3 (BtCoV) (SARS-like coronavirus HKU3)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 1596 Ident.: 95.4%
7.	P0C6T7	R1A_BCRP3 - Replicase polyprotein 1a Bat coronavirus Rp3/2004 (BtCoV/Rp3/2004) (SARS-like coronavirus Rp3)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 1592 Ident.: 95.8%
8.	A0A0U1WHG0	A0A0U1WHG0_CVHSA - 2'-O-methyltransferase BtRf-BetaCoV/JL2012	E-value: 0.0 Score: 1589 Ident.: 94.8%
9.	A0A088DIE1	A0A088DIE1_9BETC - 2'-O-methyltransferase Bat Hp-betacoronavirus/Zhejiang2013	E-value: 1e-140 Score: 1151 Ident.: 68.6%
10.	A0A1B3Q5W8	A0A1B3Q5W8_9BETC - 2'-O-methyltransferase Rousettus bat coronavirus	E-value: 2.9e-105 Score: 887 Ident.: 52.3%
11.	E0ZN43	E0ZN43_BCHK9 - 2'-O-methyltransferase Bat coronavirus HKU9-5-2	E-value: 2.2e-101 Score: 858 Ident.: 52.3%

12.	E0ZN35	E0ZN35_BCHK9 - 2'-O-methyltransferase Bat coronavirus HKU9-5-1	E-value: 5.6e-101 Score: 855 Ident.: 51.0%
13.	A0A023YA54	A0A023YA54_MERS - 3C-like proteinase BtVs-BetaCoV/SC2013	E-value: 2.7e-98 Score: 835 Ident.: 52.1%
14.	K9N638	R1A_MERS1 - Replicase polyprotein 1a Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus (isolate United Kingdom/H123990006/2012) (Betacoronavirus England 1) (Human coronavirus EMC)	E-value: 8.2e-95 Score: 809 Ident.: 50.6%
15.	T2B9I2	T2B9I2_MERS - 3C-like proteinase Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus (MERS-CoV)	E-value: 8.2e-95 Score: 809 Ident.: 50.6%
16.	U5LR11	U5LR11_9BETC - 3C-like proteinase Betacoronavirus Erinaceus/VMC/DEU/2012	E-value: 2.1e-94 Score: 806 Ident.: 51.1%
17.	P0C6U9	R1A_CVM2 - Replicase polyprotein 1a Murine coronavirus (strain 2) (MHV-2) (Murine hepatitis virus)	E-value: 5.4e-92 Score: 788 Ident.: 50.7%
18.	A3EXD8	A3EXD8_BCHK5 - 2'-O-methyltransferase Bat coronavirus HKU5-2	E-value: 5.5e-92 Score: 788 Ident.: 50.0%
19.	P0C6T5	R1A_BCHK5 - Replicase polyprotein 1a Bat coronavirus HKU5 (BtCoV) (BtCoV/HKU5/2004)	E-value: 1e-91 Score: 786 Ident.: 50.0%
20.		C0KYY5 C0KYY5_9BETC - 3C-like proteinase Murine coronavirus MHV-JHM.IA	E-value: 2.5e-91 Score: 783 Ident.: 50.7%
21.	H9AA60	H9AA60_9BETC - 3C-like proteinase Rabbit coronavirus HKU14	E-value: 4.8e-91 Score: 781 Ident.: 48.0%
22.	P0C6V1	R1A_CVMJH - Replicase polyprotein 1a Murine coronavirus (strain JHM) (MHV- JHM) (Murine hepatitis virus)	E-value: 8.7e-91 Score: 779 Ident.: 50.3%
23.	P0C6T4	R1A_BCHK4 - Replicase polyprotein 1a Bat coronavirus HKU4 (BtCoV) (BtCoV/HKU4/2004)	E-value: 1.2e-90 Score: 778 Ident.: 49.7%
RdRp			
1.	P0C6X7	R1AB_CVHSA - Replicase polyprotein 1ab Coronavirus del SARS human	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4,867 Ident.: 96.4%

2.	Q6UZF5	Q6UZF5_CVHSA - 2'-O-methyltransferase - SARS coronavirus	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4,867 Ident.: 96.4%
3.	A0A0U1WHG0	A0A0U1WHG0_CVHSA - 2'-O-methyltransferase BtRf-BetaCoV / JL2012	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4,867 Ident.: 96.2%
4.	A0A166ZL34	A0A166ZL34_9NIDO - 2'-O-methyltransferase Bat coronavirus	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4.867 Ident.: 96,2%
5.	A0A0K1YZY7	A0A0K1YZY7_SARS - 2'-O-methyltransferase-Bat SARS-like coronavirus YNLF_31C	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4,863 Ident.: 96.2%
6.	A0A0U1WHG8	A0A0U1WHG8_CVHSA - 2'-O-metiltransferase BtRf-BetaCoV / HeB2013	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4.860 Ident.: 96,1%
7.	P0C6W6	R1AB_BCRP3 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab Bat coronavirus Rp3/2004	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4,858 Ident.: 96.2%
8.	P0C6W2	R1AB_BCHK3 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Bat coronavirus HKU3	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4,851 Ident.: 95.6%
9.	P0C6V9	R1AB_BC279 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab - Bat coronavirus 279/2005	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4,850 Ident.: 95.9%
10.	R9QTA1	R9QTA1_CVHSA - ORF1b protein - Bat coronavirus Rp/Shaanxi2011	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4,482 Ident.: 96.6%
11.	A0A088DIE1	A0A088DIE1_9BETC - Non-structural polyprotein - Bat Hp-betacoronavirus/Zhejiang2013	E-value: 0.0 Score: 4,005 Ident.: 77.8%
12.	P0C6W5	R1AB_BCHK9 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Bat coronavirus HKU9	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,703 Ident.: 72.7%
13.	A0A1B3Q5W8	A0A1B3Q5W8_9BETC - 2'-O-methyltransferase-Rousettus bat coronavirus	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,687 Ident.: 72.2%
14.	A3EXI9	A3EXI9_BCHK9 - 2'-O-methyltransferase-Bat coronavirus HKU9-4	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,686 Ident.: 72.4%
15.	E0ZN59	E0ZN59_BCHK9 - 2'-O-methyltransferase-Bat coronavirus HKU9-10-2	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,680 Ident.: 72.2%

16.	E0ZN43	E0ZN43_BCHK9 - Orf1ab polyprotein -Bat coronavirus HKU9-5-2	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,673 Ident.: 72.1%
17.	E0ZN35	E0ZN35_BCHK9 - Orf1ab polyprotein -Bat coronavirus HKU9-5-1	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,668 Ident.: 72.2%
18.	U5KNA9	U5KNA9_9BETC - Orf1ab -Betacoronavirus Erinaceus/VMC/DEU/2012	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,667 Ident.: 71.5%
19.	A3EXD8	A0A0U1WHL2_BCHK5 - ORF1ab polyprotein-BtPa-BetaCoV/GD2013	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,645 Ident.: 71.0%
20.	A0A023YA54	A0A023YA54_MERS - 2'-O-methyltransferase BtVs-BetaCoV/SC2013	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,641 Ident.: 71.6%
21.	P0C6W4	R1AB_BCHK5 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Bat coronavirus HKU5	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,638 Ident.: 70.9%
22.	T2B9U0	T2B9U0_MERS - 2'-O-methyltransferase - Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,621 Ident.: 71.4%
23.	A3EXD8	3EXD8_BCHK5 - 2'-O-methyltransferase - Bat coronavirus	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,645 Ident.: 71.0%
24.	A3EXA2	A3EXA2_BCHK4 - 2'-O-methyltransferase-Bat coronavirus HKU4-2	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,617 Ident.: 71.0%
25.	K9N7C7	R1AB_MERS1 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus (isolate United Kingdom/H123990006/2012)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,615 Ident.: 71.3%
26.	P0C6W1	R1AB_BC133 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Bat coronavirus 133/2005	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,612 Ident.: 71.0%
27.	P0C6X8	R1AB_CVM2 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab - Murine coronavirus (strain 2)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,346 Ident.: 66.6%
28.	P0C6X2	R1AB_CVHN1 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Human coronavirus HKU1 (isolate N1)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,338 Ident.: 67.1%
29.	P0C6X3	R1AB_CVHN2 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Human coronavirus HKU1 (isolate N2)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,337 Ident.: 67.0%

30.	A0A140H1G9	A0A140H1G9_CVHK1 - 3C-like proteinase-Human coronavirus HKU1	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,337 Ident.: 67.1%
31.	P0C6X9	R1AB_CVMA5 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Murine coronavirus (strain A59)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,336 Ident.: 66.5%
32.	P0C6X4	R1AB_CVHN5 - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Human coronavirus HKU1 (isolate N5)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,335 Ident.: 67.0%
33.	I1TMI0	I1TMI0_9BETC - 3C-like proteinase-Rat coronavirus	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,333 Ident.: 66.4%
34.	C0KYR8	C0KYR8_9BETC - Growth factor-like peptide-Murine coronavirus RJHM/A	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,331 Ident.: 66.1%
35.	A0A0A7UXR0	A0A0A7UXR0_9BETC - 3C-like proteinase - Betacoronavirus HKU24	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,328 Ident.: 66.9%
36.	H9BZX5	H9BZX5_9BETC - 3C-like proteinase-Murine hepatitis virus strain S/3239-17	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,319 Ident.: 66.3%
37.	P0C6X6	R1AB_CVHOC - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Human coronavirus OC43	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,318 Ident.: 66.3%
38.	Q9J3E8	Q9J3E8_9BETC - Growth factor-like peptide-Murine hepatitis virus	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,317 Ident.: 65.8%
39.	H9AA60	H9AA60_9BETC - 3C-like proteinase -Rabbit coronavirus HKU14	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,314 Ident.: 66.3%
40.	P0C6W8	R1AB_CVBLU - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Bovine coronavirus (strain 98TXSF-110-LUN)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,310 Ident.: 66.1%
41.	P0C6W7	R1AB_CVBEN - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Bovine coronavirus (strain 98TXSF-110-ENT)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,310 Ident.: 66.1%
42.	P0C6Y0	R1AB_CVMJH - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Murine coronavirus (strain JHM)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,305 Ident.: 66.1%
43.	P0C6X0	R1AB_CVBQ - Replicase polyprotein 1ab-Bovine coronavirus (strain Quebec)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,301

			Ident.: 66.1%
44.	P0C6W9	R1AB_CVBM - Replicase polyprotein 1ab- Bovine coronavirus (strain Mebus)	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,294 Ident.: 65.9%
45.	Q06BE0	Q06BE0_9BETC - Growth factor-like peptide-Bovine coronavirus isolate Alpaca	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,105 Ident.: 67.3%
46.	V5TFR4	V5TFR4_9GAMC - 3C-like proteinase - Bottlenose dolphin coronavirus HKU22	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,053 Ident.: 61.0%
47.	B2BW31	B2BW31_9GAMC - 3C-like proteinase Beluga whale coronavirus SW1	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,043 Ident.: 60.8%
48.	P0C6W0	Replicase polyprotein 1ab Bat coronavirus 512/2005	E-value: 0.0 Score: 3,036 Ident.: 60.4%

*E-value: Valor esperado; †Score: Puntación; ‡Ident: Porcentaje de identidad

Figuras

	*	*
SARS_CoV2	1	SGFRKMAFPSGKVEGCMVQVTCGT TT LNGLWLDDVVYCPRHVICTSED MLNPNYEDLLIR
BtCoV_279_2	1	SGFRKMAFPSGKVEGCMVQVTCGT TT LNGLWLDDTVYCPRHVICTAED MLNPNYEDLLIR
BtRf-BetaCoV_He	1	SGFRMAFPSGKVEGCMVQVTCGT TT LNGLWLDDTVYCPRHVICTAED MLNPNYEDLLIR
SARS-CoV	1	SGFRKMAFPSGKVEGCMVQVTCGT TT LNGLWLDDTVYCPRHVICTAED MLNPNYEDLLIR
SARS-CoV_PUMC02	1	SGFRKMAFPSGKVEGCMVQVTCGT TT LNGLWLDDTVYCPRHVICTAED MLNPNYEDLLIR
BtSARS_Cov_YNLF	1	SGFRKMAFPSGKVEGCMVQVTCGT TT LNGLWLDDTVYCPRHVICTAED MLNPNYEDLLIR
BtCov_HKU3	1	SGFRKMAFPSGKVEGCMVQVTCGT TT LNGLWLDDTVYCPRHVVCTAED MLNPNYEDLLIR
BtCoV_Rp3_2	1	SGFRKMAFPSGKVEGCMVQVTCGT TT LNGLWLDDTVYCPRHVICTAED MLNPNYEDLLIR
BtRf-BetaCoV_JL	1	SGFKKVAFPSGKVEGCMVQVTCGT TT LNGLWLDDTVYCPRHVVCTVED MLNPNYEDLLIR
Bat_Hp-betaCoV	1	SGIRKMSCPTGKVERCMVRVTCGT MT LNGLWLDNTVYCPRHVMCTPEE LLAPDYDSILLR
RousBtCoV	1	AGLAKMAHPSGLVEPCIVKVSYGT MT LNGLVWLNYYVLCPRHVLC TRDDL VNPNY QRLSMR
BtCoV_HKU9-5-2	1	AGLTRMAHPSGLVEPCVVKVSYGS MT LNGLVWLDNFVVCPRHVMCS RDEL QNP YARLSMR
BtCoV_HKu9-5-1	1	AGLTRMAHPSGLVEPCVVKVSYGS MT LNGLVWLDNFVVCPRHVMCS RDEL QNP YARLSMR
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	1	SGLVKMSHPSGAVEACMVQVTCGS MT LNGLWLDNYVWCPRHVMCPAD QLNDPNYDGLLIS
MERS1_BetaC	1	SGLVKMSHPSGDVEACMVQVTCGS MT LNGLWLDNTVWCPRHVMCPAD QLSDPNYDALLIS
MERS-CoV	1	SGLVKMSHPSGDVEACMVQVTCGS MT LNGLWLDNTVWCPRHVMCPAD QLSDPNYDALLIS
BetaCoV_Erinace	1	SGLVKMAHPSGAVEQCIQVTCGS MT LNGLWLDNIVYCPRHVMCPQD QLVDPNYDALLNS
MuHepatitis	1	SGIVKMFPTSKVEPCVVSVTYGN MT LNGLWLDDKVYCPRHVICSSAD MTDPDYSNLLCR
BtCoV_HKU5-2	1	SGLVKMAAPSGVVENCMVQVTCGS MT LNGLWLDNYVWCPRHVMCPAD QLSDPNYDALLVS
BtCoV_HKU5	1	SGLVKMAAPSGVVENCMVQVTCGS MT LNGLWLDNYVWCPRHVMCPAD QLSDPNYDALLVS
MuCoV_JHM	1	SGIVKMVSPTSKVEPCVVSVTYGN MT LNGLWLDDKVYCPRHVICSSAD MTDPDYPNLLCR
RaCoV_HKU14	1	SGIVKMVSPTSKVEPCVVSVTYGN MT LNGLWLDDKVYCPRHVICSSAD MTNPDYPNLLCR
MuCoV_hepat	1	SGIVKMVSPTSKVEPCVVSVTYGN MT LNGLWLDDKVYCPRHVICSSAD MTDPDYPNLLCR
BtCoV_HKU4	1	SGLVKMSAPSGAVENCIVQVTCGS MT LNGLWLDNTVWCPRHIMCPAD QLTDPNYDALLIS
SARS_CoV2	61	KSNHNFLVQAG---NVQLRVIGHSMQNCVLLKLVDTANPKTPKYKFVRIQPGQTF SVLAC
BtCoV_279_2	61	KSNHSFLVQAG---NVQLRVIGHSMQNC LLRL KVDT SNPK TPKYKFVRIQPGQTF SVLAC
BtRf-BetaCoV_He	61	KSNHSFLVQAG---NVQLRVIGHSMQNC LLRL KVDT SNPK TPKYKFVRIQPGQTF SVLAC
SARS-CoV	61	KSNHSFLVQAG---NVQLRVIGHSMQNC LLRL KVDT SNPK TPKYKFVRIQPGQTF SVLAC
SARS-CoV_PUMC02	61	KSNHSFLVQAG---NVQLRVIGHSMQNC LLRL KVDT SNPK TPKYKFVRIQPGQTF SVLAC
BtSARS_Cov_YNLF	61	KSNHSFLVQAG---NVQLRVIGHSMQNC LLRL KVDT SNPK TPKYKFVRIQPGQTF SVLAC
BtCov_HKU3	61	KSNHSFLVQAG---NVQLRVIGHSMQNC LLRL KVDT SNPK TPKYKFVRIQPGQTF SVLAC
BtCoV_Rp3_2	61	KSNHSFLVQAG---NVQLRVIGHSMQNC LLRL KVDT SNPK TPKYKFVRIQPGQTF SVLAC
BtRf-BetaCoV_JL	61	KSNHSFLVQAG---NVQLRVIGHSMQNC LLRL KVDT SNPK TPKYKFVRIQPGQTF SVLAC
Bat_Hp-betaCoV	61	KATHSFTVQYG---TAYLKVVSYKMTGSVLQ LGVDQ INPETPKYKFVRAKPGATF SVLAC
RousBtCoV	61	AANYDFHVSQN---GLNLRVTGHVMEGALLR LTVD ATNP KTPA HSFVRVSTGQ AISILAC
BtCoV_HKU9-5-2	61	AANYDFHVSHN---GHNIRVIGHVMVGS LLKLTVD VNNP RTPA YSFIRVSTGQ AMSLLAC
BtCoV_HKu9-5-1	61	AANYDFHVSHN---GHNIRVIGHVMVGS LLKLTVD VNNP RTPA YSFIRVSTGQ AMSLLAC
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	61	MTNHSFTVQKHVGAPANLRVIGHAMQ GTL LLK LTVD SPNP TPA YFTFT VKPG ASF SVLAC
MERS1_BetaC	61	MTNHSFSVQKHIGAPANLRVVGHAMQ GTL LLK LTVD ANP TPA YFTFT VKPG AA FSVLAC
MERS-CoV	61	MTNHSFSVQKHIGAPANLRVVGHAMQ GTL LLK LTVD ANP TPA YFTFT VKPG AA FSVLAC
BetaCoV_Erinace	61	MTNHSFTIQRHGRSTANLRCTGHAMH GTL LLK LTVD SANP TPA YFTFT IKQ SS FSVLAC
MuHepatitis	61	VISSDFCVMSG---RMSLTVMSYQ MQG SL LV LT VT LQNP TPK YSFGV VKPG ET F TV LAA
BtC15oV_HKU5-2	61	KTNLSFIVQKNVGAPANLRVVGHTMV GTL LLK LAV ESAN PQ TPAYFTFT VKPG ASF SVLAC
BtCoV_HKU5	61	KTNLSFIVQKNVGAPANLRVVGHTMV GTL LLK LAV ESAN PQ TPAYFTFT VKPG ASF SVLAC
MuCoV_JHM	61	VTSSDFCVMSD---RMSLTVMSYQ MQG SL LV LT VT LQNP TPK YSFGV VKPG ET F TV LAA
RaCoV_HKU14	61	VTSSDFTIMSD---RMSLTVMSYQ MQG CM LV LT IT LQNP TPK YTFGV VKPG ET F TV LAA
MuCoV_hepat	61	VTSSDFCVMSD---RMSLTVMSYQ MQG SL LV LT VT LQNP TPK YSFGV VKPG ET F TV LAA
BtCoV_HKU4	61	KTNHSFIVQKHIGAQANLRVVAHSMV GVL LLK LTVD ANP TPA YFT STV K PG ASF SVLAC

Figura Suplementaria 1. Alineamiento múltiple de secuencias de Mpro del SARS-CoV-2 y virus homólogos. Los residuos marcados en rojo representan los aminoácidos que interactúan con los inhibidores Carmofur y N3. (*) Indica aquellos residuos poco conservados en el sitio de unión de inhibidores.

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SARS_CoV2	118	YNGSPSGVYQCAMRPNFTIKGS	FLNGSCGSGVGFNIDYDCVSFCYMHMMELPTGVHAGTDL
BtCoV_279_2	118	YNGSPSGVYQCAMRPNYTIKGS	FLNGSCGSGVGFNIDYDCVSFCYMHMMELPTGVHAGTDL
BtRf-BetaCoV_He	118	YNGSPSGVYQCAMRPNYTIKGS	FLNGSCGSGVGFNIDYDCVSFCYMHMMELPTGVHAGTDL
SARS-CoV	118	YNGSPSGVYQCAMRPNHTIKGS	FLNGSCGSGVGFNIDYDCVSFCYMHMMELPTGVHAGTDL
SARS-CoV_PUMC02	118	YNGSPSGVYQCAMRPNHTIKGS	FLNGSCGSGVGFNIDYDCVSFCYMHMMELPTGVHAGTDL
BtSARS_Cov_YNLF	118	YNGSPSGVYQCAMRPNHTIKGS	FLNGSCGSGVGFNIDYDCVSFCYMHMMELPTGVHAGTDL
BtCov_HKU3	118	YNGSPSGVYQCAMRPNHTIKGS	FLNGSCGSGVGFNIDYDCVSFCYMHMMELPTGVHAGTDL
BtCoV_Rp3_2	118	YNGSPSGVYQCAMRPNHTIKGS	FLNGSCGSGVGFNIDYDCVSFCYMHMMELPTEVHAGTDL
BtRf-BetaCoV_JL	118	YNGSPSGVYQCAMRPNYTIKGS	FLNGSCGSGVGFNIDYDCVSFCYMHMMELPTGVHAGTDL
Bat_Hp-betaCoV	118	YNGMPAGVYQVAMRPNHTIKGS	FLNGSCGSGVGYTLGYDRVEFCYMHMMELPTGVHTGTDL
RousBtCoV	118	YDGI PAGVYTCTLRANGLRAA	FLCGSCGSPGFVMNGKEVQFCYLHQLELPTNGHTGTDM
BtCoV_HKU9-5-2	118	YDGVPTGVYTCTLRNGLTKAS	FLCGSCGSPGFVMNGKEVQFCYHQLELPTNGHTGTDM
BtCoV_HKu9-5-1	118	YDGVPTGVYTCTLRNGLTKAS	FLCGSCGSPGFVMNGKEVQFCYHQLELPTNGHTGTDM
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	121	YNGRPTGFTFVVMRPNHTIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYTKEGNVINFYCYMHQMELANGHTGSSSF
MERS1_BetaC	121	YNGRPTGFTFVVMRPNYTIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYTKEGVSINFYCYMHQMELANGHTGSAF
MERS-CoV	121	YNGRPTGFTFVVMRPNYTIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYTKEGVSINFYCYMHQMELANGHTGSAF
BetaCoV_Erinace	121	YNGRPSGTYTVMRPNSTIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYVKEGNVINFYCYMHQMELANGHTGSSSF
MuHepatitis	118	YNGKSQGAHFVMTMRSSYTIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYVLTGDSVRFVYMHQLELSTGCHTGTDF
BtCoV_HKU5-2	121	YNGRPTGVFVMNMRQNSTIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYTQEGNVINFYCYMHQMELANGHTGCSF
BtCoV_HKU5	121	YNGRPTGVFVMNMRQNSTIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYTQEGNVINFYCYMHQMELANGHTGCAF
MuCoV_JHM	118	YNGRPQGAFHVVMRSSHITIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYVLTGDSVRFVYMHQLELSTGCHTGTDF
RaCoV_HKU14	118	YNGRPQGAFHVMTMRSSFTIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYVLMGDCVKFVYMHQLELSTGCHTGTDF
MuCoV_hepat	118	YNGRPQGAFHVVMRSSHITIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYVLTGDSVRFVYMHQLELSTGCHTGTDF
BtCoV_HKU4	121	YNGKPTGVFTVNLRHNSTIKGS	FLCGSCGSGVGYTENGGVINFFVYMHQMELANGHTGSSSF

* **

SARS_CoV2	178	EGNFYGPFFVDRQTAQAAGTDTTITVNVLAWLYAAVINGDRWFLNRFTTTLNDFNLVAMKY
BtCoV_279_2	178	EGKFYGPFFVDRQTAQAAGTDTTITLNLVLAWLYAAVINGDRWFLNRFTTTLNDFNLVAMKY
BtRf-BetaCoV_He	178	EGKFYGPFFVDRQTAQAAGTDTTITLNLVLAWLYAAVINGDRWFLNRFTTTLNDFNLVAMKY
SARS-CoV	178	EGKFYGPFFVDRQTAQAAGTDTTITLNLVLAWLYAAVINGDRWFLNRFTTTLNDFNLVAMKY
SARS-CoV_PUMC02	178	EGKFYGPFFVDRQTAQAAGTDTTITLNLVLAWLYAAVINGDRWFLNRFTTTLNDFNLVAMKY
BtSARS_Cov_YNLF	178	EGKFYGPFFVDRQTAQAAGTDTTITLNLVLAWLYAAVINGDRWFLNRFTTTLNDFNLVAMKY
BtCov_HKU3	178	EGKFYGPFFVDRQTAQAAGTDTTITLNLVLAWLYAAVINGDRWFLNRFTTTLNDFNLVAMKY
BtCoV_Rp3_2	178	EGKFYGPFFVDRQTAQAAGTDTTITLNLVLAWLYAAVINGDRWFLNRFTTTLNDFNLVAMKY
BtRf-BetaCoV_JL	178	EGKFYGPFFVDRQTAQAAGTDTTITLNLVLAWLYAAVINGDRWFLNRFTTTLNDFNLVAMKY
Bat_Hp-betaCoV	178	EGTFYGDFFVDRQTSQSAGSDNTLTLNLVLAWLYAAVINGERWFIVPQTCALDFNTAVLKY
RousBtCoV	178	HGAFYGPFFE DKQVPQLASPDVITITVNVLAWLYAAVLSGESWVTKLGITAAEFNTSAVKY
BtCoV_HKU9-5-2	178	SGVfygpffe DKQVPQLAAPDCTITVNVLAWLYAAVLSGENWFLTKSSITPAEFNNAVKY
BtCoV_HKu9-5-1	178	SGVfygpffe DKQVPQLAAPDCTITVNVLAWLYAAVLSGENWFLTKSSITPAEFNNAVKY
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	181	DGNMYGAFQDRQVHQVQLTDKYCTVNI VAWLYAAI LNC TWFVKP SRTSVVS FNEWAMAN
MERS1_BetaC	181	DGTMYGAFM DKQVHQVQLTDKYCSVNVVAVWLYAAI LNC AWFVKP NRTSVVS FNEWALAN
MERS-CoV	181	DGTMYGAFM DKQVHQVQLTDKYCSVNVVAVWLYAAI LNC AWFVKP NRTSVVS FNEWALAN
BetaCoV_Erinace	181	DGNMYGNFQDRQIYQAQLSDKHCTINNVAVWLYAAV LNC NWFVKP NKTGVAA FNEWALS N
MuHepatitis	178	SGNFYGPYR DAQVVQLPVQDYTQTVNVVAVWLYAAI LNC NWFVQSDSCS LEEFN VWAMTN
BtCoV_HKU5-2	181	DGVMYGAFEDRQVHQVQLSDKYCTINIVAVWLYAAI LNC NWFVKP NKTGIAT FNEWAMSN
BtCoV_HKU5	181	DGVMYGAFEDRQVHQVQLSDKYCTINIVAVWLYAAI LNC NWFVKP NKTGIAT FNEWAMSN
MuCoV_JHM	178	SGNFYGPYR DAQVVQLPVQDYTQTVNVVAVWLYAAI LNC NWFVQSDSCS LEEFN VWAMTN
RaCoV_HKU14	178	NGDFYGPYK DAQVVQLPVQDYVQSVNFVAVWLYAAI LNC NWFVQSDRCS IEDYN VWAMSN
MuCoV_hepat	178	SGNFYGPYR DAQVVQLPVQDYTQTVNVVAVWLYAAI LNC NWFVQSDSCS LEEFN VWAMTN
BtCoV_HKU4	181	DGVMYGAFEDKQTHQLQLTDKYCTINNVAVWLYAAV LNC KWFVKP TRVGI VTYNEWALS N

Figura Suplementaria 1. Continuación.

SARS_CoV2	238	NYEPLTQDHVDILGPLSAQTGIAVLDMCASLKELLQNGMNGRTILGSALLEDEFTPFDDV
BtCoV_279_2	238	NYEPLTQDHVDILGPLSAQTGIAVLDMCAALKELLQNGMNGRTILGSTILEDEFTPFDDV
BtRf-BetaCoV_He	238	NYEPLTQDHVDILGPLSAQTGIAVLDMCAALKELLQNGMNGRTILGSTILEDEFTPFDDV
SARS-CoV	238	NYEPLTQDHVDILGPLSAQTGIAVLDMCAALKELLQNGMNGRTILGSTILEDEFTPFDDV
SARS-CoV_PUMC02	238	NYEPLTQDHVDILGPLSAQTGIAVLDMCAALKELLQNGMNGRTILGSTILEDEFTPFDDV
BtSARS_Cov_YNLF	238	NYEPLTQDHVDVILGPLSAQTGIAVLDMCAALKELLQNGMNGRTILGSTILEDEFTPFDDV
BtCov_HKU3	238	NYEPLTQDHVDILGPLSAQTGIAVLDMCAALKELLQNGMNGRTILGSTILEDEFTPFDDV
BtCoV_Rp3_2	238	NYEPLTQDHVDILGPLSAQTGIAVLDMCAALKELLQNGMNGRTILGSTILEDEFTPFDDV
BtRf-BetaCoV_JL	238	NYEPLTQDHVDILGPLSAQTGIAVLDMCAALKELLQNGMNGRTILGSTILEDEFTPFDDV
Bat_Hp-betaCoV	238	GYQSLTEDGVAALDPLVAQTGISVQTMCASLKDLLVHGMGRGRCILSSPTLEDEFTPFDDV
RousBtCoV	238	MCQSVTEESLQVLQPLAAKTGVSQVRLSSLVLLSTGFCGKTIMGSCSLEDEHTPYDIG
BtCoV_HKU9-5-2	238	MCQSVSSDSLQVLQPLAAKTGISVERMLSALKVLLSTGFCGRTIMGSCSLEDEHTPYDIG
BtCoV_HKu9-5-1	238	MCQSVSSDSLQVLQPLAAKTGISVGRMLSALKVLLSTGFCGRTIMGSCSLEDEHTPYDIG
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	241	QFTEFIGT--HALDMLAVKTGVSVEQLLSAIQQL-NQGFQKQILGSSMLEDEFTPEDVN
MERS1_BetaC	241	QFTEFVGT--QSVDMLAVKTGVAIEQLLYAIQQL-YTGFQKQILGSTMLEDEFTPEDVN
MERS-CoV	241	QFTEFVGT--QSVDMLAVKTGVAIEQLLYAIQQL-YTGFQKQILGSTMLEDEFTPEDVN
BetaCoV_Erinace	241	QFTEFVST--QALELLAVKTGVQIEQLLYSIQQL-NNGFQGNVILGSAMLEDEYTPEDVN
MuHepatitis	238	GFSSIKAD--LVLDALASMTGVTVEQILAAIKRL-YSGFQKQILGSCVLEDELTPSDVY
BtCoV_HKU5-2	241	QFTEFIGT--QSVDMLAHKTGVSVEQLLYAIQTL-HKGFQKQILGNSMLEDEFTPDDVN
BtCoV_HKU5	241	QFTEFIGT--QSVDMLAHKTGVSVEQLLYAIQTL-HKGFQKQILGNSMLEDEFTPDDVN
MuCoV_JHM	238	GFSSIKAD--LVLDALASMTGVTVEQMLAAIKRL-HSGFQKQILGSCVLEDELTPSDVY
RaCoV_HKU14	238	GFSQIKSD--LVLDALASMTGVLENLLAAIKRL-HKGFQGRQIMGSCAFEDDELTPSDVY
MuCoV_hepat	238	GFSSIKAD--LVLDALASMTGVTVEQVLAIAIKRL-HSGFQKQILGSCVLEDELTPSDVY
BtCoV_HKU4	241	QFTEFVGT--QSIDMLAHRGTGVSVEQMLAAIQSL-HAGFQKQILGSTLEDEFTPDDVN

SARS_CoV2	298	RQCSGVTFQ
BtCoV_279_2	298	RQCSGVTFQ
BtRf-BetaCoV_He	298	RQCSGVTFQ
SARS-CoV	298	RQCSGVTFQ
SARS-CoV_PUMC02	298	RQCSGVTFQ
BtSARS_Cov_YNLF	298	RQCSGVTFQ
BtCov_HKU3	298	RQCSGVTFQ
BtCoV_Rp3_2	298	RQCSGVTFQ
BtRf-BetaCoV_JL	298	RQCSGVTFQ
Bat_Hp-betaCoV	298	RQCSGVTLQ
RousBtCoV	298	RQMLGVTLQ
BtCoV_HKU9-5-2	298	RQMLGVKLQ
BtCoV_HKu9-5-1	298	RQMLGVKLQ
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	298	MQIMGVVMQ
MERS1_BetaC	298	MQIMGVVMQ
MERS-CoV	298	MQIMGVVMQ
BetaCoV_Erinace	298	MQMMGVVMQ
MuHepatitis	295	QQLAGVKLQ
BtCoV_HKU5-2	298	MQVMGVVMQ
BtCoV_HKU5	298	MQVMGVVMQ
MuCoV_JHM	295	QQLAGVKLQ
RaCoV_HKU14	295	QQLAGVKLQ
MuCoV_hepat	295	QQLAGVKLQ
BtCoV_HKU4	298	MQVMGVVMQ

Figura Suplementaria 1. Continuación.

SARS-COV 1 SADASTFLNRVCGVS-AARLTPCGTGTSTDVVYRAFDIYN--EKVAGFAKFLKTNCCRFQ
SARS-COV-PUMC02 1 SADASTFLNRVCGVS-AARLTPCGTGTSTDVVYRAFDIYN--EKVAGFAKFLKTNCCRFQ
BetaCoV_JL2012 1 SADASPFLNRVCGVS-AARLTPCGTGTSTDVVYRAFDIYN--EKVAGFAKFLKTNCCRFQ
BAT-COV 1 SADASPFLNRVCGVS-AARLTPCGTGTSTDVVYRAFDIYN--EKVAGFAKFLKTNCCRFQ
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7 1 SADASTFLNRVCGVS-AARLTPCGTGTSTDVVYRAFDIYN--EKVAGFAKFLKTNCCRFQ
BtRf-BETACOV_He 1 SADASAFLNRVCGVS-AARLTPCGTGTSTDVVYRAFDIYN--EKVAGFAKFLKTNCCRFQ
BAT-COV-Rp3_200 1 SADASTFLNRVCGVS-AARLTPCGTGTSTDVVYRAFDIYN--EKVAGFAKFLKTNCCRFQ
BAT-COV-HKU3 1 SADASTFLNRVCGVS-AARLTPCGTGTSTDVVYRAFDIYN--EKVAGFAKFLKTNCCRFQ
BAT-COV-279_200 1 SADASTFLNRVCGVS-AARLTPCGTGTSTDVVYRAFDIYN--ERVAGFAKFLKTNCCRFQ
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa 1 -----
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe 1 -----SFLNRVRGVS-AARLTPCGSGLSTDVVVRAFDLYN--SKIIGFGLRYKGNCCRFQ
BAT-COV-HKU9 1 -----ECFLNRVRGTSGVARLVPLGSGVQPDIVLRAFDICN--TKVAGFGLHLKNNCCRYQ
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C 1 AND-DCFLNRVRGASGVARLVPLGIGVQPDVVLRAFDICN--SKVAGFGLHLKNNCCRYQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-4 1 -----ECFLNRVRGTSGVARLVPLGSGVQPDIVLRAFDICN--TKVAGFGLHLKNNCCRYQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-10 1 AKD-ECFLNRVRGTSGVARLVPLGSGVQPDVVLRAFDICN--TKVAGFGLHLKNNCCRYQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-5- 1 AKD-ECFLNRVRGTSGVARLVPLGSGVQPDVVLRAFDICN--TKVAGFGLHLKNNCCRYQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-10 1 -----FLNRVRGTSGVARLVPLGSGVEPDIVLRAFDICN--TKVAGFGLHLKNNCCRYQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-3 1 -----FLNRVRGTSGVARLVPLGSGVEPDIVLRAFDICN--TKVAGFGLHLKNNCCRYQ
BETACOV-ERINACE 1 -----NFLNRVRGSIVDARIEPCASGLATDVVYRAFDICNYKARVAGIGKHYKTNTCRFV
BAT-COV-HKU5-2 1 -----NFLNRVRGSIVNARIEPCASGLTTDVVFRAFDICNYKAKVAGIGKYYKTNTCRFV
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC 1 -----NFLNRVRGSIVNARIEPCASGLSTDVVFRAFDICNYKAKVAGIGKYYKTNTCRFV
BAT-COV-HKU5 1 ---PTNFLNRVRGSIVNARIEPCASGLTTDVVFRAFDICNYKAKVAGIGKYYKTNTCRFV
MERS-COV 1 -----NFLNRVRGSIVNARIEPCSSGLSTDVVFRAFDICNYKAKVAGIGKYYKTNTCRFV
BAT-COV-HKU4-2 1 -----NFLNRVRGSSVNARLEPCSSGLTTDVVYRAFDICNFKARVAGIGKYYKTNTCRFV
MERS-COV-ISK_20 1 -----NFLKRVRGSIVNARIEPCSSGLSTDVVFRAFDICNYKAKVAGIGKYYKTNTCRFV
BAT-COV-133_200 1 -----NFLNRVRGSSVNARLEPCSSGLTTDVVYRAFDICNFKARVAGIGKYYKTNTCRFV
MURINE-COV 1 -----NFLNRVRGTSVNARLVPCASGLD TDVQLRAFDICN--ANRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
HUMAN-COV-HKU1- 1 -----NFLNRVRGTSVNARLVPCASGLSTDVQLRAFDICN--TNRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_ 1 -----NFLNRVRGTSVNARLVPCASGLSTDVQLRAFDICN--TNRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_ 1 ---MQNFLNRVRGTSVNARLVPCASGLSTDVQLRAFDICN--TNRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
MURINE-COV-A59 1 -----NFLNRIRGTSVNARLVPCASGLD TDVQLRAFDICN--ANRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_ 1 -----NFLNRVRGTSVNARLVPCASGLSTDVQLRAFDICN--TNRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
RAT-COV 1 -----NFLKRVRGTSVNARLVPCASGLD TDVQLRAFDICN--ANRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
MURINE-COV-RJHM 1 SVKRHEFFKRVRGTSVNARLVPCASGLD TDVQLRAFDICN--ANRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
BETA-COV-HKU24 1 -----NFLNRVRGASVDARLVPCASGLSTDVQKRAFDICN--ANVAGIGLHYKVNCCRFQ
MURINE-HEP-17 1 -----NFLKRVRGTSVNARLVPCASGLD TDVQLRAFDICN--AYRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
HUMAN-COV-OC43 1 -----NFLNRVRGASVDARLVPCASGLSTDVQLRAFDIYN--ASVAGIGLHLKVNCCRFQ
MURINE-HEP-VIRU 1 SVKRHELKRVIRGTSVNARLVPCASGLD TDVQLRAFDICN--ANRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
RABBIT-COV-HKU1 1 -----NFLNRVRGASVDARLVPCATGLSTDVQLRAFDICN--ASVAGIGLHLKVNCCRFQ
BOVINE-COV-98LU 1 -----NFLNRVRGTSVDARLVPCASGLSTDVQLRAFDICN--ASVAGIGLHLKVNCCRFQ
BOVINE-COV-98EN 1 -----NFLNRVRGTSVDARLVPCASGLSTDVQLRAFDICN--ASVAGIGLHLKVNCCRFQ
MURINE-COV-JHM 1 -----NFLNRVRGTSVNARLVPCASGLD TDVQLRAFDICN--ANRAGIGLYYKVNCCRFQ
BOVINE-COV-BEC 1 -----NFLNRVRGTSVDARLVPCASGLSTDVQLRAFDICN--ASVAGIGLHLKVNCCRFQ
BOVINE-COV-MEBU 1 -----NFLNRVRGTSVDARLVPCASGLSTDVQLRAFDICN--ASVAGIGLHLKVNCCRFQ
BOVINE-COV-Alpa 1 -----
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU 1 ----QNYLNRVRGLS-EARLRPCASGLLPDVVKRAFDLYN--SNTAGMYASLKHNCARFQ
BEL-WHALE-COV_S 1 ----QNYLNRVRGLS-EARLRPCASGLLPDVVKRAFDLYN--SNTAGMYASLKHNCARFQ
BAT-COV-512_200 1 -----YLNVRVGSS-AARLEPL-NGSDTHHVFRADFVYN--RDVACISKFLKVNCCVRLK

Figura Suplementaria 2. Alineamiento múltiple de secuencias de RdRp del SARS-CoV-2 y virus homólogos. Los residuos en rojo representan los aminoácidos que interactúan con el inhibidor Remdesivir.

SARS-COV-2	58	EKDEDDNLIDSYFVVKRHTFSNYQHEETIYNLLKDCPAVAKHDFFKFRIDGDMVPHISRQ
SARS-COV	58	EKDEEGNLLDSYFVVKRHTMSNYQHEETIYNLVKDCPAVAVHDFFKFRVDGDMVPHISRQ
SARS-COV-PUMC02	58	EKDEEGNLLDSYFVVKRHTMSNYQHEETIYNLVKDCPAVAVHDFFKFRVDGDMVPHISRQ
BetaCoV_JL2012	58	EMDEDGNLIDSYFVVKRHTMSNYQHEEAIYNLLKECPAVAVHDFFKFRVDGDMVPHISRQ
BAT-COV	58	EMDEDGNLIDSYFVVKRHTMSNYQHEEAIYNLLKECPAVAVHDFFKFRVDGDMVPHISRQ
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	58	EKDEEGNLLDSYFVVKRHTMSNYQHEETIYNLVKDCPAVAVHDFFKFRVDGDMVPHISRQ
BtRf-BETACOV_He	58	EKDEEGNLLDSYFVVKRHTMSNYQHEEAIYNLLKECPAVAVHDFFKFRVDGDMVPHISRQ
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	58	EKDEEGNLLDSYFVVKRHTMSNYQHEETIYNLVKDCPAVAVHDFFKFRVDGDMVPHISRQ
BAT-COV-HKU3	58	EKDEEGNLLDSYFVVKRHTMSNYQHEETIYNLIKECPAVAVHDFFKFRVDGDMVPHISRQ
BAT-COV-279_200	58	EKDEEGNLLDSYFVVKRHTMSNYQHEETIYNLVKECPAVAVHDFFKFRVDGDMVPHISRQ
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	1	-----SNYQHEETIYNLVKECPAVAVHDFFKFRVDGDMVPHISRQ
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	53	EIDEDGKALDSFFIVKRHTEDNFKLEQEMYDLLKDSGVAHVHDFHFRVEGRMEPHITRQ
BAT-COV-HKU9	55	ELDADGTQLDSYFVVKRHTESNYLLEQRCYEKLLKDCGVVARHDFFKFNIEGVMTPHVSRE
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	58	ELDSEGNKLLDSYFVVKRHTTEENYALEQRCYDKLKDCDVARHDFFKFVVEGVMTPHISRQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	55	ELDADGTQLDSYFVVKRHTESNYLLEQRCYEKLLKDCGVVARHDFFKFNIEGVMTPHVSRE
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	58	ELDAEGNQLDSYFVVKRHTESNYLLEQRCYEKLLKDCGVVARHDFFKFNIDGEMTPHVSRE
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	58	ELDAEGNQLDSYFVVKRHTESNYLLEQRCYEKLLKDCGVVARHDFFKFNIDGEMTPHVSRE
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	53	ELDVDGVQLDSYFVVKRHTESNYLLEQRCYEKLLKDCGVVARHDFFKFNIEGVMTPHVSRE
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	53	ELDVDGVQLDSYFVVKRHTESNYLLEQRCYEKLLKDCGVVARHDFFKFNIEGVMTPHVSRE
BETACOV-ERINACE	56	ELDDQGHKLLDSYFVVKRHTMENYELEKRCYDLVKDCDAVAVHDFFIIDVDKVKTPHIVRQ
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	56	EVDDEGHRLDSFFVVKRHTMENYELEKRCYDLVKDCDAVAVHDFFIIDVDKVKTPHIVRQ
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	56	EKDDQGHQLDSYFVVKRHTMENYELEKRCYDLVKDCDAVAVHDFFIIDVDKVKTPHIVRQ
BAT-COV-HKU5	58	EVDDEGHRLDSFFVVKRHTMENYELEKRCYDLVKDCDAVAVHDFFIIDVDKVKTPHIVRQ
MERS-COV	56	ELDDQGHLLDSYFVVKRHTMENYELEKHCYDLLRDCDAVAPHDFFIIDVDKVKTPHIVRQ
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	56	QVDDEGHKLLDSYFIVKRHTMSNYELEKRCYDLLKDCDAVAIHDFFIIDVDKVKTPHIVRQ
MERS-COV-ISK_20	56	ELDDQGHLLDSYFVVKRHTMENYELEKHCYDLLRDCDAVAPHDFFIIDVDKVKTPHIVRQ
BAT-COV-133_200	56	QVDDEGHKLLDSYFIVKRHTMSNYELEKRCYDLLKDCDAVAIHDFFIIDVDKVKTPHIVRQ
MURINE-COV	54	RADEDGNTLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKECEYELTKECGVVAEHEFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	54	RIDDDGNKLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKTYEELTKSCGVVAEHDFFTFDIDGSRVPHIVRR
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	54	RIDDDGNKLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKTYEELTKSCGVVAEHDFFTFDIDGSRVPHIVRK
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	56	RIDDDGNKLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKTYEELTKSCGVVAEHDFFTFDIDGSRVPHIVRR
MURINE-COV-A59	54	RVDEDGNKLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKECEYELTKECGVVAEHEFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	54	RIDDDGNKLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKTYEELTKSCGVVAEHDFFTFDIDGSRVPHIVRR
RAT-COV	54	RVDEDGNKLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKECEYELTKECGVVAEHEFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
MURINE-COV-RJHM	59	RVDEDGNKLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKECEYELTKDCGVVAEHEFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
BETA-COV-HKU24	54	CAEEDGTLLDQYFVVKRTGLDIYDKEKACYERLKDCSVVAVHDFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
MURINE-HEP-17	54	CVDEYGNKLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKECEYELTKDCGVVAEHEFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
HUMAN-COV-OC43	54	RVDENGDKLDQFFVVKRTDLTIYNREMKCYERVKDCKFVAEHDFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	59	RVDEDGNKLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKECEYELTKECGVVAEHEFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	54	RLDESGNKMDRFFVVKRTDLVTYNREMECYERVKGCRVVAEHDFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
BOVINE-COV-98LU	54	RVDENGDKLDQFFVVKRTDLTIYNREMECYERVKDCKFVAEHDFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
BOVINE-COV-98EN	54	RVDENGDKLDQFFVVKRTDLTIYNREMECYERVKDCKFVAEHDFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
MURINE-COV-JHM	54	RVDEEGNKLDKFFVVKRTNLEVYNKEKECEYELTKDCGVVAEHEFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
BOVINE-COV-BEC	54	RVDENGDKLDQFFVVKRTDLTIYNREMECYERVKDCKFVAEHDFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	54	RVDENGDKLDQFFVVKRTDLTIYNREMECYERVKDCKFVAEHDFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	1	-----YERVKDCKFVAEHDFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRK
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	54	ELDENDDEIDSFFVVKQTTPHNFEHEEKCYLDLK-ADCVAVHDFFRFEG----MYNICRQ
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	54	ELDENDDEIDSFFVVKQTTPHNFEHEEKCYLDLK-ADCVAVHDFFRFEG----MYSICRQ
BAT-COV-512_200	51	NLDK----HDAFWIVKCKTKSVMEHEQSIYNLISDCGAVAKHDFFTWKEGRSVYGNVCRQ

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	118	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDDYFNKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAN
SARS-COV	118	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDDYFNKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAN
SARS-COV-PUMC02	118	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDDYFNKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAN
BetaCoV_JL2012	118	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDDYFNKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAN
BAT-COV	118	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDDYFNKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAN
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	118	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDDYFNKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAN
BtRf-BETACOV_He	118	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDDYFNKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAN
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	118	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDDYFNKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAN
BAT-COV-HKU3	118	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDNYFNKKDWYDFVENPDVLRVYAN
BAT-COV-279_200	118	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDDYFNKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAN
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	41	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDEGNCDTLKEILVTYNCCDDDYFNKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAN
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	113	RLTKYTMADLVYALRHFDENSCEVLKEILVTYNCCGSDYFEKKDWYDFVENPDIILRVYAR
BAT-COV-HKU9	115	RLTKYTMADLVYSLRHFDDNNNCEILKEILVLRGCGCTADYFDRKDWYDFVENPDIIRVYHN
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	118	RLTKYTMADLVYSLRHFDDNNNCEILKEILVLRGCGCDEEFFTKKDWYDFVETPELISVYHK
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	115	RLTKYTMADLVYSLRHFDDNNNCDTLKEILVLRGCGCTADYFDKDWYDFVENPDIIRVYHK
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	118	RLTKYTMADLVYSLRHFDDNNNCDMLKEILVLRGCGCTEDYFDRKDWYDFVENPDIIRVYHK
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	118	RLTKYTMADLVYSLRHFDDNNNCDMLKEILVLRGCGCTEDYFDRKDWYDFVENPDIIRVYHK
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	113	RLTKYTMADLVYSLRHFDDNNNCDTLKEILVLRGCGCTSDYFDRADWYDFVENPDIIRVYHK
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	113	RLTKYTMADLVYSLRHFDDNNNCDTLKEILVLRGCGCTSDYFDRADWYDFVENPDIIRVYHK
BETACOV-ERINACE	116	RLTEYTMMDLVYALRHFDDQNNCEVLKTIILVRYGCGCEESYFDNKLWDFVENPDVIRVYHK
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	116	RLTEYTMMDLVYALRHFDDQNNCEVLKSIILVKYGCCDASYFDNKLWDFVENPNVIVSVYHK
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	116	RLTEYTMMDLVYALRHFDDQNNCEVLKSIILVKYGCCDASYFDNKLWDFVENPNVIGVYHK
BAT-COV-HKU5	118	RLTEYTMMDLVYALRHFDDQNNCEVLKSIILVKYGCCDASYFDNKLWDFVENPNVIVSVYHK
MERS-COV	116	RLTEYTMMDLVYALRHFDDQN-SEVLKAILVKYGCCDVITYFENKLWDFVENPNSVIGVYHK
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	116	SLTEYTMMDLVYALRHFDDQNNCEVLKSIILVKYGCCQSYFDNKLWDFVENPNSVIGVYHK
MERS-COV-ISK_20	116	RLTEYTMMDLVYALRHFDDQN-SEVLKAILVKYGCCDVITYFENKLWDFVENPNSVIGVYHK
BAT-COV-133_200	116	SLTEYTMMDLVYALRHFDDQNNCEVLKSIILVKYGCCQSYFDNKLWDFVENPNSVIGVYHK
MURINE-COV	114	DLSKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSTLKEILLTYAECDESYFQKKDWYDFVENSDIINVIYKK
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	114	NLSKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSILCEILCEYADCKESYFQKKDWYDFVENPDIINIYKK
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	114	NLSKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSILCEILCEYADCKESYFQKKDWYDFVENPDIINIYKK
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	116	NLSKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSILCEILCEYADCKESYFQKKDWYDFVENPDIINIYKK
MURINE-COV-A59	114	DLSKFTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSTLKEILLTYAECDESYFQKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	114	NLSKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSILCEILCEYADCKESYFQKKDWYDFVENPDIINIYKK
RAT-COV	114	DLSKFTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSTLKEILLTYAECGESYFQKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
MURINE-COV-RJHM	119	DLSKFTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSTLKEILLTYAECDESYFQKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
BETA-COV-HKU24	114	YLTKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSLLCDILCLYAECEQSYFTKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
MURINE-HEP-17	114	DLSKFTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSTLKEILLTYAECDESYFQKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
HUMAN-COV-OC43	114	DLTKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCMLLCDILSIYAGCEQSYFTKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	119	DLSKFTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSTLKEILLTYAECDESYFQKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	114	DLTKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSLLCDILSMYAGCEQSYFTQKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
BOVINE-COV-98LU	114	DLTKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCMLLCDILSIYAGCEQSYFTKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
BOVINE-COV-98EN	114	DLTKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCMLLCDILSIYAGCEQSYFTKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
MURINE-COV-JHM	114	DLSKFTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCSTLKEILLTYAECDESYFQKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
BOVINE-COV-BEC	114	DLTKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCMLLCDILSIYAGCEQSYFTKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	114	DLTKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCMLLCDILSIYAGCEQSYFTKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	32	DLTKYTMDLDCYALRHFDRNDCMLLCDILSIYAGCEQSYFTKKDWYDFVENPDIINVIYKK
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	109	RLTKYTMDLDCYAFRHFDPNDCDVLKEILVVKGCCEWDYFDQPNWYDFVENPDWFLISR
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	109	RLTKYTMDLDCYAFRHFDPNDCDVLKEILVVKGCCEWDYFDQPNWYDFVENPDWFLISR
BAT-COV-512_200	107	DLTEYTMMDLDCYALRHFDENNCEITLKKILVVVGACDESYFDNKLWDFVENEDVHRVYAK

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	178	LGGERVQRALLKTVQFCDAMRNAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFIQTTTPGSGVPPVDSY
SARS-COV	178	LGGERVQRSLKTVQFCDAMRDAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVAPGCGVPIVDSY
SARS-COV-PUMC02	178	LGGERVQRSLKTVQFCDAMRDAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVAPGCGVPIVDSY
BetaCoV_JL2012	178	LGGERVQRALLKTVQFCDAMRDAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVTPGCGVPIVDSY
BAT-COV	178	LGGERVQRALLKTVQFCDAMRDAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVTPGCGVPIVDSY
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	178	LGGERVQRALLKTVQFCDAMRDAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVAPGCGVPIVDSY
BtRf-BETACOV_He	178	LGGERVQRALLKTVQFCDAMRDAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVAPGCGVPIVDSY
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	178	LGGERVQRALLKTVQFCDAMRDAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVAPGCGVPIVDSY
BAT-COV-HKU3	178	LGGERVRRALLKTVQFCDAMRDAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVAPGCGVPIVDSY
BAT-COV-279_200	178	LGGERVQRALLKTVQFCDAMRDAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVAPGCGVPIVDSY
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	101	LGGERVQRALLKTVQFCDAMRDAGIVGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVAPGCGVPIVDSY
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	173	LGGERIRCNLLKTVKFCDAKMRHGI VGVLTLDNQDLNNGNWDYDFGDFVQVAPGCGVPIVDSY
BAT-COV-HKU9	175	LGETVVRKAVLSAVKMAADSMVQGLIGVLTLDNQDLNNGQWYDFGDFIEGAPAGVAVMDTY
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	178	LGETVVRNAVLSANKMADAMVKAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDFIEAPPGTGVAVMDTY
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	175	LGETVVRKAVLSAVKMAADSMVQGLIGVLTLDNQDLNNGQWYDFGDFIEGAPAGVAVMDTY
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	178	LGETVVRKAVLSAVEMADAMVEQGLIGVLTLDNQDLNNGQWYDFGDFIEGAPAGVAVMDTY
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	178	LGETVVRKAVLSAVEMADAMVEQGLIGVLTLDNQDLNNGQWYDFGDFIEGAPAGVAVMDTY
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	173	LGETVVRNAVLSATKADAMVEQGLIGVLTLDNQDLNNGQWYDFGDFIEGAPAGVAVMDTY
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	173	LGETVVRNAVLSATKADAMVEQGLIGVLTLDNQDLNNGQWYDFGDFIEGAPAGVAVMDTY
BETACOV-ERINACE	176	LGELVRRAMLSTVKFCDHMVKSGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDFVVTQPGAGVAIVDSY
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	176	LGGERIRQAVLNTVKFCQDMVKSGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDFVITQPGAGVAIVDSY
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	176	LGGERIRKAVLNTVKFCQDMVKSGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGLWYDFGDFVITQPGSGVAVVDSY
BAT-COV-HKU5	178	LGGERIRQAVLNTVKFCQDMVKSGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDFVITQPGAGVAIVDSY
MERS-COV	175	LGGERVQAILNTVKFCDHMVKAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDFVITQPGSGVAIVDSY
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	176	LGGERIRQAVLNTVKMCDHMKVSGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDFVITQPGAGVAIVDSY
MERS-COV-ISK_20	175	LGGERVQAILNTVKFCDHMVKAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDFVITQPGSGVAIVDSY
BAT-COV-133_200	176	LGGERIRQAVLNTVKMCDHMKVSGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDFVITQPGAGVAIVDSY
MURINE-COV	174	LGPIFNRRALLNTAKFADTLVEAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFVKTVPGCGVAVADSY
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	174	LGPIFNRRALLNTVIFADTLVEVGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFIQTAPGFGVAVADSY
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	174	LGPIFNRRALLNTVIFADTLVKVGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFIQTAPGFGVAVADSY
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	176	LGPIFNRRALLNTVIFADTLVEVGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFIQTAPGFGVAVADSY
MURINE-COV-A59	174	LGPIFNRRALLNTAKFADALVEAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFVKTVPGCGVAVADSY
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	174	LGPIFNRRALLNTVIFADTLVEVGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFIQTAPGFGVAVADSY
RAT-COV	174	LGPIFNRRALLNTAKFADALVEAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFVKTVPGCGVAVADSY
MURINE-COV-RJHM	179	LGPIFNRRALLNTAKFADTLVEAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFVKTVPGCGVAVADSY
BETA-COV-HKU24	174	LGPIFNRRALLNTAKFADAMVEAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGIWDYDFGDFVLAAPGCGVAIADSY
MURINE-HEP-17	174	LGPIFNRRALLNTAKFADALVEAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFVKTVPGCGVAVADSY
HUMAN-COV-OC43	174	LGPIFNRRALVSATEFADKLVEVGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDYVIAAPGCGVAIADSY
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	179	LGPIFNRRALLNTAKFADALVEAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFVKTVPGCGVAVADSY
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	174	LGPIFNRRALVNTAEFADALVEAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNNGMWDYDFGDYVITAPGCGVAVADSY
BOVINE-COV-98LU	174	LGPIFNRRALVSATEFADKLVEVGLVGI LTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDYVIAAPGCGVAIADSY
BOVINE-COV-98EN	174	LGPIFNRRALVSATEFADKLVEVGLVGI LTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDYVIAAPGCGVAIADSY
MURINE-COV-JHM	174	LGPIFNRRALLNTANFADTLVEAGLVGVLTLDNQDLNGQWYDFGDFVKTVPCCGVAVADSY
BOVINE-COV-BEC	174	LGPIFNRRALVSATEFADKLVEVGLVGI LTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDYVIAAPGCGVAIADSY
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	174	LGPIFNRRALVSATEFADKLVEVGLVGI LTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDYVIAAPGCGVAIADSY
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	92	LGPIFNRRALVSATEFADKLVEVGLVGI LTLDNQDLNNGKWDYDFGDYVIAAPGCGVAIADSY
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	169	LGPIFQRALIKVAEFCDLMVEKGYIGVVTLDNQDLNNGNFYDFGDFKVKVLPGCGVPTTSY
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	169	LGPIFQRALIKVAEFCDLMVEKGYIGVVTLDNQDLNNGNFYDFGDFKVKVLPGCGVPTTSY
BAT-COV-512_200	167	LGTIVARAMLKCVKYCDAMVEQGI VGVITLDNQDLNNGDFYDFGDFVTSVKMGVPICTSY

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	238	YSLLMPIILTLTRALTAESHVDTDL-TKPYIKWDLKLYDFTEERLKLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
SARS-COV	238	YSLLMPIILTLTRALAAESHMDADL-AKPLIKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
SARS-COV-PUMC02	238	YSLLMPIILTLTRALAAESHMDADL-AKPLIKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
BetaCoV_JL2012	238	YSLLMPIILTLTRALAAESHMDTDL-TKPLIKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
BAT-COV	238	YSLLMPIILTLTRALAAESHMDTDL-TKPLIKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	238	YSLLMPIILTMTRALAAESHMDADL-AKPLIKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
BtRf-BETACOV_He	238	YSLLMPIILTLTRALAAESHMDADL-TKPLIKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	238	YSLLMPIILTLTRALAAESHMDADL-AKPLIKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
BAT-COV-HKU3	238	YSLLMPIILTLTKALAAESHMDADL-AKPLVKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
BAT-COV-279_200	238	YSLLMPIILTLTKALAAESHMDADL-AKPLIKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	161	YSLLMPIVLTTLTRALAAESHMDADR-TKPLIKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDQTYHP
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	233	YSLLMPLMTMTKMLAEETHVDCDL-TKDHVKWDLKLYDFTEERLCLFDYFVKYWDMPYHP
BAT-COV-HKU9	235	YSLAMPVYTMTNMLAAECHVDGDF-SKPKRVDLCKYDYTQFKYSLFSKYFVKYWDMPYHP
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	238	YSLAMPVYTMTNMLAAECHVDGDL-TKPKRVWDLCKYDYTQFKYSLFQKYFVKYWDMPYHP
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	235	YSLAMPVYTMTNMLAAECHVDGDL-GKPKRVWDICKYDYTQFKYSLFSKYFVKYWDMPYHP
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	238	YSLAMPVYTMTNMLAAECHVDGDF-SKPKRVDLCKYDYTQFKYSLFNKYFKHWDMPYHP
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	238	YSLAMPVYTMTNMLAAECHVDGDF-SKPKRVDLCKYDYTQFKYSLFNKYFKHWDMPYHP
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	233	YSLAMPVYTMTNMLAAESHIDGDL-SKPKRVDICTYDYTQFKYSLFSKYFKHWDMPYHP
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	233	YSLAMPVYTMTNMLAAESHIDGDL-SKPKRVDICTYDYTQFKYSLFSKYFKHWDMPYHP
BETACOV-ERINACE	236	YSYLMPLVLSMTDALAAETHKDCDL-SKPLIEWSLLDYDFTDYKCLFEKYFKHWDMPYHP
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	236	YSYLMPLVLSMTNCLAAETHRDCDL-TKPLIEWPLLEYDYTDYKIGLFEKYFKHWDMPYHP
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	236	YSYLMPLVLSMTDCLAAETHRDCDL-NKPLIEWPLLEYDYTDYKIGLFEKYFKHWDMPYHP
BAT-COV-HKU5	238	YSYLMPLVLSMTNCLAAETHRDCDL-TKPLIEWPLLEYDYTDYKIGLFEKYFKHWDMPYHP
MERS-COV	235	YSYLMPLVLSMTDCLAAETHRDCDF-NKPLIEWPLLEYDYTDYKIGLFEKYFKYWDMPYHP
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	236	YSYLMPLVLSMTNCLAAETHKDCDF-NKPLIEWPLLEYDYTDYKIGLFEKYFKYWDMPYHP
MERS-COV-ISK_20	235	YSYLMPLVLSMTDCLAAETHRDCDF-NKPLIEWPLLEYDYTDYKIGLFEKYFKYWDMPYHP
BAT-COV-133_200	236	YSYLMPLVLSMTNCLAAETHKDCDF-NKPLIEWLLEYDYTDYKIGLFEKYFKHWDMPYHP
MURINE-COV	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELFVNG-----TYREFDLVQYDFTDFKLELFNKYFKYWSMPTYHP
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	234	YSYMPMLTMCHVLDCELFVND-----SYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKYWSMPTYHP
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	234	YSYMPMLTMCHVLDCELFVND-----SYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKYWSMPTYHP
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	236	YSYMPMLTMCHVLDCELFVND-----SYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKYWSMPTYHP
MURINE-COV-A59	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELFVNG-----TYREFDLVQYDFTDFKLELFTKYFKHWSMPTYHP
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	234	YSYMPMLTMCHVLDCELFVND-----SYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKYWSMPTYHP
RAT-COV	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELYVNG-----TYREFDLVQYDFTDFKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
MURINE-COV-RJHM	239	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELFVNG-----TYREFDLVQYDFTDFKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
BETA-COV-HKU24	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELYVNG-----AYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKYWSMPTYHP
MURINE-HEP-17	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELFVNG-----TYREFDLVQYDFTDFKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
HUMAN-COV-OC43	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELYVNN-----AYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	239	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELFVNG-----TYREFDLVQYDFTDFKLELFTKYFKHWSMPTYHP
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELYVNN-----TYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
BOVINE-COV-98LU	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELYVNN-----AYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
BOVINE-COV-98EN	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELYVNN-----AYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
MURINE-COV-JHM	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELFVNG-----TYREFDLVQYDFTDFKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
BOVINE-COV-BEC	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELYVNN-----AYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	234	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELYVNN-----AYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	152	YSYMPMLTMCHALDSELYVNN-----AYRQFDLVQYDFTDYKLELFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	229	YSYMPCLTACDALASERFFEFKA-TSGYKQYDLTKYDFTEEKQLQFLMKYFKYWDRTYHP
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	229	YSYMPCLTACDALASERFFEFKA-TSGYKQYDLTKYDFTEEKQLQFLMKYFKYWDRTYHP
BAT-COV-512_200	227	YSYMPVGMNTCLASECFIKSDIFGEDFRFTDLLAYDFTEHKVNLFNKYFKHWSMPTYHP

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	297	NCVNCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
SARS-COV	297	NCINCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
SARS-COV-PUMC02	297	NCINCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
BetaCoV_JL2012	297	NCINCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKMFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
BAT-COV	297	NCINCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKMFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	297	NCINCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
BtRf-BETACOV_He	297	NCINCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	297	NCINCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
BAT-COV-HKU3	297	NCINCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
BAT-COV-279_200	297	NCINCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	220	NCINCLDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TVFPPTSFGPLVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	292	NCQSCPDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	TIPQTSFGPIVKRIYVDGVPFV	VSTGYHFRELGVVHN
BAT-COV-HKU9	294	NCVACADDRCILHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTSFGPLVQKIYVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	297	NCVACPDDRCILHCANFNILFS	SMVIPNTSFGPLVQKVYVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVIN
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	294	NCVACADDRCILHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTSFGPLVQKIYVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	297	NCVACTDDRCILHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTSFGPLVQKIYVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	297	NCVACADDRCILHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTSFGPLVQKIYVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	292	NCVACADDRCILHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTSFGPLVQKIYVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	292	NCVACADDRCILHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTSFGPLVQKIYVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BETACOV-ERINACE	295	NCVNCVDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	SMTLPKTCFGPLVRKVYVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGLVMN
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	295	NCVNCTDDRCVLHCANFNVLFS	SMTLPKTCFGPIVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGLVMN
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	295	NCVACADDRCVLHCANFNVLFS	SMTMPKTCFGPIVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGLVMN
BAT-COV-HKU5	297	NCVNCTDDRCVLHCANFNVLFS	SMTLPKTCFGPIVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGLVMN
MERS-COV	294	NCVNCTDDRCVLHCANFNVLFS	AMTMPKTCFGPIVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGLVMN
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	295	NCVNCSDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	SMVLPNTSFGPIVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGLVMN
MERS-COV-ISK_20	294	NCVNCTDDRCVLHCANFNVLFS	AMTMPKTCFGPIVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGLVMN
BAT-COV-133_200	295	NCVNCGDDRCILHCANFNVLFS	SMVLPNTSFGPIVRKIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGLVMN
MURINE-COV	289	NTCECEDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPKTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	289	NTVDCDNDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	289	NTVDCDNDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	291	NTVDCDNDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
MURINE-COV-A59	289	NTCECEDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPKTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	289	NTVDCDNDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
RAT-COV	289	NTCECEDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPKTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
MURINE-COV-RJHM	294	NTSECEDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPKTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BETA-COV-HKU24	289	NTCDCEDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
MURINE-HEP-17	289	NTCECEDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPKTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
HUMAN-COV-OC43	289	NTVDCQDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	294	NTCECEDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPKTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	289	NTIDCQDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BOVINE-COV-98LU	289	NTVDCQDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BOVINE-COV-98EN	289	NTVDCQDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
MURINE-COV-JHM	289	NTSECEDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPKTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BOVINE-COV-BEC	289	NTVDCQDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	289	NTVDCQDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	207	NTVDCQDDRCIIHCANFNILFS	SMVLPNTCFGPLVRQIFVDGVPFV	VSTGYHYRELGVVMN
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	288	NCVECIDDRCLIIHCANFNILFS	FATLFPQTAFGCLCKRVYIDGVPFV	VSTGYHRELGVLLN
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	288	NCVECIDDRCLIIHCANFNILFS	FATLFPQTAFGCLCKRVYIDGVPFV	VSTGYHRELGVLLN
BAT-COV-512_200	287	NCEDCHDESCIVHCANFNILFS	TLPITAFGPLCRKWCWIDGVPFV	VSTGYHRELGVVMN

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	357	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
SARS-COV	357	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
SARS-COV-PUMC02	357	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
BetaCoV_JL2012	357	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
BAT-COV	357	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	357	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
BtRf-BETACOV_He	357	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	357	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
BAT-COV-HKU3	357	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
BAT-COV-279_200	357	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	280	QDVNLHSSRSLFKELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDKRTSCFSVAALTNNVAFQTVKPGNFN
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	352	QDIHVHNARLSLRELLVYAADPAMHAASGTLTLLDKRTTCFSVAALTNTVVFQTVKPGNFN
BAT-COV-HKU9	354	QDIRQHAQRLSLRELLVYAADPAMHVAASNALADKRTVCMSVAAMTTGVTFFQTVKPGQFN
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	357	QDIKVHSQRSLSKDLLVYAADPAMHIAASHALADKRTVCMSVAAMTTGVTFFQTVKPGQFN
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	354	QDIRQHAQRLSLRELLVYAADPAMHVAASNALADKRTVCMSVAAMTTGVTFFQTVKPGQFN
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	357	QDIRQHAQRLSLRELLVYAADPAMHVAASNALADKRTVCMSVAAMTTGVTFFQTVKPGQFN
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	357	QDIRQHAQRLSLRELLVYAADPAMHVAASNALADKRTVCMSVAAMTTGVTFFQTVKPGQFN
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	352	QDVRQHAQRLSLRELLVYAADPAMHVAASNALADKRTVCMSVAAMTTGVTFFQTVKPGQFN
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	352	QDVRQHAQRLSLRELLVYAADPAMHVAASNALADKRTVCMSVAAMTTGVTFFQTVKPGQFN
BETACOV-ERINACE	355	MDVNMHSHRSLKELMYYAADPAMHVASSNALLDLRTSCFSVAALATGLTFQTVRPGNFN
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	355	MDVSLHRHRLSLKELMYYAADPAMHIASASALWDLRTPCFSVAALTTGLTFQTVRPGNFN
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	355	MDVSLHRHRLSLKELMYYAADPAMHIASSNALLDLRTSCFSVAALTTGLTFQTVRPGNFN
BAT-COV-HKU5	357	MDVSLHRHRLSLKELMYYAADPAMHIASASALWDLRTPCFSVAALTTGLTFQTVRPGNFN
MERS-COV	354	MDVSLHRHRLSLKELMYYAADPAMHIASSNAFLDLRTSCFSVAALTTGLTFQTVRPGNFN
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	355	MDFNIHRHRLALKELMYYAADPAMHIASASALWDLRTPCFSVAALTTGLTFQTVRPGNFN
MERS-COV-ISK_20	354	MDVSLHRHRLSLKELMYYAADPAMHIASSNAFLDLRTSCFSVAALTTGLTFQTVRPGNFN
BAT-COV-133_200	355	MDVNIHRHRLALKELMYYAADPAMHIASASALWDLRTPCFSVAALTTGLTFQTVRPGNFN
MURINE-COV	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	349	LDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPAMHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGIKFQTVKPGNFN
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	349	LDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPAMHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGIKFQTVKPGNFN
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	351	LDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPAMHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGIKFQTVKPGNFN
MURINE-COV-A59	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	349	LDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPAMHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGIKFQTVKPGNFN
RAT-COV	349	MDXDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
MURINE-COV-RJHM	354	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
BETA-COV-HKU24	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASANALYDLRTCCFSVAAIASGVKFQTVKPGNFN
MURINE-HEP-17	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
HUMAN-COV-OC43	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALYDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	354	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASATALYDLRTCCFSVAAIASGVKFQTVKPGNFN
BOVINE-COV-98LU	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALYDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
BOVINE-COV-98EN	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALYDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
MURINE-COV-JHM	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALLDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
BOVINE-COV-BEC	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALYDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	349	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALYDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	267	MDVDTHRYRLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALYDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFN
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	348	KDNSMSFSKMSIGELMRFAADPSLLVSASDAFVLDLRTSCFSLSALSTGLTYQTVKPGHFN
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	348	KDNSMSFSKMSIGELMRFAADPSLLVSASDAFVLDLRTSCFSLSALSTGLTYQTVKPGHFN
BAT-COV-512_200	347	KDLNLHSSRLTINELLQFCADPSLLIASSPALVDKRTVCFSVAALGTGMTNQTVKPGHFN

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	417	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
SARS-COV	417	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
SARS-COV-PUMC02	417	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
BetaCoV_JL2012	417	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
BAT-COV	417	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	417	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
BtRf-BETACOV_He	417	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	417	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
BAT-COV-HKU3	417	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
BAT-COV-279_200	417	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	340	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVELKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIRQLLFVVEVV
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	412	KDFYDFAVSKGFFKEGSSVDLKHFFFAQDGNAAITDYSYYRYNLPTMCDIKQLLFTMEVV
BAT-COV-HKU9	414	EDFYNFAVKCGFFKEGSTISFKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIKQLLFSLEVV
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	417	EDFYKFAVKCGFFKEGSSISFKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIKQLLFSLEVV
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	414	EDFYNFAVKCGFFKEGSTISFKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIKQLLFSLEVV
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	417	EDFYKFAVKCGFFKEGSSISFKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDFYRYNLPTMCDIKQLLFSLEVV
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	417	EDFYKFAVKCGFFKEGSSISFKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDFYRYNLPTMCDIKQLLFSLEVV
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	412	EDFYNFALKCGFFKEGSTISFKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIKQLLFSLEVV
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	412	EDFYNFALKCGFFKEGSTISFKHFFFAQDGNAAISDYDYRYNLPTMCDIKQLLFSLEVV
BETACOV-ERINACE	415	QDFYDFVSKGFFKEGSSVTLKHFFFAQDGHAAITDYNYYSYNLPTMCDIKQLLFCLEVV
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	415	KDFYDFVSKGFFKEGSSVTLRHFFFAQDGHAAITDYSYYAYNLPTMCDIKQMLFCMEVV
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	415	QDFYDFVSKGFFKEGSSVTLKHFFFAQDGHAAITDYNYYSYNLPTMCDIKQMLFCMEVV
BAT-COV-HKU5	417	KDFYDFVSKGFFKEGSSVTLRHFFFAQDGHAAITDYSYYAYNLPTMCDIKQMLFCMEVV
MERS-COV	414	QDFYDFVSKGFFKEGSSVTLKHFFFAQDGNAAITDYNYYSYNLPTMCDIKQMLFCMEVV
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	415	KDFYDFVSRGFFKEGSSVTLKHFFFAQDGHAAITDYSYYAYNLPTMVDIKQMLFCMEVV
MERS-COV-ISK_20	414	QDFYDFVSKGFFKEGSSVTLKHFFFAQDGNAAITDYNYYSYNLPTMCDIKQMLFCMEVV
BAT-COV-133_200	415	KDFYDFVSRGFFKEGSSVTLKHFFFAQDGHAAITDYSYYAYNLPTMVDIKQMLFCMEVV
MURINE-COV	409	QDFYEFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	409	QDFYEFVSKGLFKEGSTVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	409	QDFYEFVSKGLFKEGSTVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	411	QDFYEFVSKGLFKEGSTVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
MURINE-COV-A59	409	QDFYEFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	409	QDFYEFVSKGLFKEGSTVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
RAT-COV	409	QDFYEFILSKGLFKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
MURINE-COV-RJHM	414	QDFYEFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
BETA-COV-HKU24	409	QDFYDFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLRHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFCLEVV
MURINE-HEP-17	409	QDFYEFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
HUMAN-COV-OC43	409	QDFYDFVLSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	414	QDFYEFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	409	QDFYDFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
BOVINE-COV-98LU	409	QDFYDFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
BOVINE-COV-98EN	409	QDFYDFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
MURINE-COV-JHM	409	QDFYEFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVVEVV
BOVINE-COV-BEC	409	QDFYDFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	409	QDFYDFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	327	QDFYDFILSKGLLKEGSSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFLVLEVV
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	408	EDFYNFAEKKGFFKEGSSISPLKHFFFIQDGNAAIADFDYRFRNKPTMVDIQQFLFCFEVT
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	408	EDFYNFAEKKGFFKEGSSISPLKHFFFIQDGNAAIADFDYRFRNKPTMVDIQQFLFCFEVT
BAT-COV-512_200	407	REFYDFLRSQGFFEEGSELTLKHFFFAQKGDAAVRDFDYRYNRRTVLDICQARVVYQIV

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
SARS-COV	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
SARS-COV-PUMC02	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BetaCoV_JL2012	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BtRf-BETACOV_He	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-HKU3	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-279_200	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	400	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	472	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-HKU9	474	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	477	DRYFDCYEGGCLQASQVVVANYDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	474	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	477	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	472	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	472	DKYFDCYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BETACOV-ERINACE	475	NKYFDIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	475	DRYFDCYEGGCLQASQVVVANYDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	475	NKYFDIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-HKU5	477	DRYFDCYEGGCLQASQVVVANYDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
MERS-COV	474	NKYFDIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	475	DKYFDIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
MERS-COV-ISK_20	474	NKYFDIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-133_200	475	DKYFDIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
MURINE-COV	469	NKYFDIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	469	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	469	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	471	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
MURINE-COV-A59	469	NKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	469	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
RAT-COV	469	NKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
MURINE-COV-RJHM	474	NKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BETA-COV-HKU24	469	FKYFEVYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
MURINE-HEP-17	469	NKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
HUMAN-COV-OC43	469	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	474	NKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	469	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BOVINE-COV-98LU	469	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BOVINE-COV-98EN	469	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
MURINE-COV-JHM	469	NKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BOVINE-COV-BEC	469	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	469	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	387	YKYFEIYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	468	DKYFEQYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	468	DKYFEQYDGGCINANQVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI
BAT-COV-512_200	467	QCYFGMYEGGCITAKEVIVNNLDKSAGFPFNKVGKARLYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKRNVI

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
SARS-COV	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
SARS-COV-PUMC02	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
BetaCoV_JL2012	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
BAT-COV	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
BtRf-BETACOV_He	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
BAT-COV-HKU3	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
BAT-COV-279_200	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	460	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKLLKSLAATRGATV	VIGTSKIFYG
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	532	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ICSTMTNRQFHQKMLKSLAATRNVSV	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-HKU9	534	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	IASTMTNRQFHQKMLKSLIAAARGASV	VIGTTKIFYG
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	537	PTVTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	IASTMTNRQFHQKILKSLIAAARGASV	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	534	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	IASTMTNRQFHQKMLKSLIAAARGASV	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	IASTMTNRQFHQKMLKSLIAAARGASV	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	IASTMTNRQFHQKMLKSLIAAARGASV	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	532	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	IASTMTNRQFHQKMLKSLIAAARGASV	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	532	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	IASTMTNRQFHQKMLKSLIAAARGASV	VIGTTKIFYG
BETACOV-ERINACE	535	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTNRQYHQKMLKSMAATRGATC	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	535	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTNRQYHQKMLKSMAATRGATC	VIGTTKIFYG
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	535	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTNRQYHQKMLKSMAATRGATC	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-HKU5	537	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTNRQYHQKMLKSMAATRGATC	VIGTTKIFYG
MERS-COV	534	PTMTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTNRQYHQKMLKSMAATRGATC	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	535	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTNRQYHQKMLKSMAATRGATC	VIGTTKIFYG
MERS-COV-ISK_20	534	PTMTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTNRQYHQKMLKSMAATRGATC	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-133_200	535	PTITQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTNRQYHQKMLKSMAATRGATC	VIGTTKIFYG
MURINE-COV	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	531	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
MURINE-COV-A59	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
RAT-COV	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
MURINE-COV-RJHM	534	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
BETA-COV-HKU24	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVSV	VIGTTKIFYG
MURINE-HEP-17	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
HUMAN-COV-OC43	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	534	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
BOVINE-COV-98LU	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
BOVINE-COV-98EN	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
MURINE-COV-JHM	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
BOVINE-COV-BEC	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	529	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	447	PFLTQMNLKYAISAKNRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSLAATRGVPV	VIGTTKIFYG
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	528	PTITQINMKYAISAKSRARTVAGVSI	ILSTMTNRQFHQKCLKSLVNTRNATV	VIGTTKIFYG
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	528	PTITQINMKYAISAKSRARTVAGVSI	ILSSMTNRQFHQKCLKSLVNTRNATV	VIGTTKIFYG
BAT-COV-512_200	527	PTMTQLNLKYAISGKDRARTVGGVSL	LSTMTTRQYHQKHLKSLVNTRGASV	VIGTTKIFYG

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	597	GWHNMLKTVYSDVENPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLVLARKHTTCCSLSHRFYRLA
SARS-COV	597	GWHNMLKTVYSDVETPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLVLARKHNTCCNLSHRFYRLA
SARS-COV-PUMC02	597	GWHNMLKTVYSDVETPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLVLARKHNTCCNLSHRFYRLA
BetaCoV_JL2012	597	GWHNMLKTVYSDVETPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLVLARKHSTCCNLSHRFYRLA
BAT-COV	597	GWHNMLKTVYSDVETPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLVLARKHSTCCNLSHRFYRLA
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	597	GWHNMLKTVYSDVETPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLVLARKHSTCCNLSHRFYRLA
BtRf-BETACOV_He	597	GWHNMLKTVYSDVETPYLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLVLARKHSTCCNLSHRFYRLA
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	597	GWHNMLKTVYSDVETPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLVLARKHSTCCNLSHRFYRLA
BAT-COV-HKU3	597	GWHNMLKTVYSDVESPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLILARKHSTCCNLSHRFYRLA
BAT-COV-279_200	597	GWHNMLKTVYSDVETPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLVLARKHSTCCNLSHRFYRLA
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	520	GWHNMLKTVYSDVETPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIMASLVLARKHSTCCNLSHRFYRLA
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	592	GWNMLKTLTYADVDNAQLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMLRIFASLILARKHNTCCNVSEYRYRLA
BAT-COV-HKU9	594	GWNRMRLRTLCEGVENPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNLLRIFASLILARKHATCCNASERFYRLA
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	597	GWNRMRLRTLCDGVEKPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNLLRIFASLILARKHSTCCNTSERFYRLA
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	594	GWNRMRLRTLCEGVENPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNLLRIFASLILARKHATCCNASERFYRLA
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	597	GWNRMRLRTLCEGVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNLLRIFASLILARKHATCCNASERFYRLA
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	597	GWNRMRLRTLCEGVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNLLRIFASLILARKHATCCNASERFYRLA
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	592	GWNRMRLRTLCEGVESPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNLLRIFASLILARKHSTCCNASERFYRLA
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	592	GWNRMRLRTLCEGVESPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNLLRIFASLILARKHSTCCNASERFYRLA
BETACOV-ERINACE	595	GWDFMLKTLTYKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMCRIASLVLARKHSTCCNTSDRFYRLA
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	595	GWDFMLKTLTYKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMCRIASLILARKHSTCCNTSDRFYRLA
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	595	GWDFMLRTLTYKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMCRIASLILARKHGTCCCTTRDRFYRLA
BAT-COV-HKU5	597	GWDFMLKTLTYKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMCRIASLILARKHSTCCNTSDRFYRLA
MERS-COV	594	GWDFMLKTLTYKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMCRIASLILARKHGTCCCTTRDRFYRLA
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	595	GWDFMLKTLTYKDVESPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMCRIASLILARKHSTCCNTSDRFYRLA
MERS-COV-ISK_20	594	GWDFMLKTLTYKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMCRIASLILARKHGTCCCTTRDRFYRLA
BAT-COV-133_200	595	GWDFMLKTLTYKDVESPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNMCRIASLILARKHSTCCNTSDRFYRLA
MURINE-COV	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDSPVLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHDSCCSHTDRFYRLA
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	589	GWDDMLRHLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHEFCCSHGDRFYRLA
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	589	GWDDMLRHLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHEFCCSHGDRFYRLA
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	591	GWDDMLRHLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHEFCCSHGDRFYRLA
MURINE-COV-A59	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDSPVLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHDSCCSHTDRFYRLA
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	589	GWDDMLRHLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHEFCCSHGDRFYRLA
RAT-COV	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDSPVLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHDSCCSHTDRFYRLA
MURINE-COV-RJHM	594	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDSPVLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHDSCCSHTDRFYRLA
BETA-COV-HKU24	589	GWDDMLCRLIKGVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRILSSLVLARKHDACCSTDRFYRLA
MURINE-HEP-17	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDSPVLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHDSCCSHTDRFYRLA
HUMAN-COV-OC43	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHETCCSQSDRFYRLA
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	594	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDSPVLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHDSCCSHTDRFYRLA
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHDACCSTDRFYRLA
BOVINE-COV-98LU	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHEACCSTDRFYRLA
BOVINE-COV-98EN	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHEACCSTDRFYRLA
MURINE-COV-JHM	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDSPVLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHDSCCSHTDRFYRLA
BOVINE-COV-BEC	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHEACCSTDRFYRLA
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	589	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHEACCSTDRFYRLA
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	507	GWDDMLRRLIKDVDPHLMGWDPKCDRAMPNILRIVSSLVLARKHEACCSTDRFYRLA
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	588	GWDNMLRNLMRGVEDPVLMGWDPKCDRAMPNLLRILASLILARRHKGCCDWNERIYRLA
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	588	GWDNMLRNLMRGVEDPVLMGWDPKCDRAMPNLLRILASLILARRHKGCCDWNERIYRLA
BAT-COV-512_200	587	GWDNMLKTLIKDVENPHLMGWDPKCDRALPNMIRMISAMILGSKHVNCCSSSDRYRLC

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2 657 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
SARS-COV 657 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
SARS-COV-PUMC02 657 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
BetaCoV_JL2012 657 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
BAT-COV 657 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7 657 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
BtRf-BETACOV_He 657 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
BAT-COV-Rp3_200 657 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
BAT-COV-HKU3 657 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
BAT-COV-279_200 657 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa 580 NECAQVLSEVMVMCGGSLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANVNALLSTDGKNKIA
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe 652 NECAQVLSEMVLCGGGALYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNICQAVTANISALLAANGNKIV
BAT-COV-HKU9 654 NECAQVLSEMVLCGGGFYVKPGGTS **SGDST**TAYANSVFNICQAVSANLNTFLSIDGNKIY
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C 657 NECAQVLSEIVLCGGGFYVKPGGTS **SGDST**TAYANSVFNICQAVSANLNTFLSRDGNKIY
BAT-COV-HKU9-4 654 NECAQVLSEMVLCGGGFYVKPGGTS **SGDST**TAYANSVFNICQAVSANLNTFLSIDGNKIY
BAT-COV-HKU9-10 657 NECAQVLSEMVLCGGGFYVKPGGTS **SGDST**TAYANSVFNICQAVSANLNTFLSIDGNKIY
BAT-COV-HKU9-5- 657 NECAQVLSEMVLCGGGFYVKPGGTS **SGDST**TAYANSVFNICQAVSANLNTFLSIDGNKIY
BAT-COV-HKU9-10 652 NECAQVLSEMVLCGGGFYVKPGGTS **SGDST**TAYANSVFNICQAVSANLNTFLSIDGNKIY
BAT-COV-HKU9-3 652 NECAQVLSEMVLCGGGFYVKPGGTS **SGDST**TAYANSVFNICQAVSANLNTFLSIDGNKIY
BETACOV-ERINACE 655 NECAQVLSEYVLCGGGYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNIIQAVTSNVSALMSANGNKII
BAT-COV-HKU5-2 655 NECAQVLSEYVLCGGGYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNIIQATTANVSALMGANGNTIV
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC 655 NECAQVLSEYVLCGGGYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNIIQATTANVSALMGANGNKIV
BAT-COV-HKU5 657 NECAQVLSEYVLCGGGYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNIIQATTANVSALMGANGNTIV
MERS-COV 654 NECAQVLSEYVLCGGGYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNIIQATTANVSALMGANGNKIV
BAT-COV-HKU4-2 655 NECAQVLSEYVLCGGGYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNIIQATTANVSALMSANGNTII
MERS-COV-ISK_20 654 NECAQVLSEYVLCGGGYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNIIQATTANVSALMGANGNKIV
BAT-COV-133_200 655 NECAQVLSEYVLCGGGYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNIIQATTANVSALMSANGNTII
MURINE-COV 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGHKIE
HUMAN-COV-HKU1- 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVTANVCSLMACNGHKIE
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_ 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVTANVCSLMACNGHKIE
HUMAN-COV-HKU1 651 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVTANVCSLMACNGHKIE
MURINE-COV-A59 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGHKIE
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_ 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVTANVCSLMACNGHKIE
RAT-COV 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGHKIE
MURINE-COV-RJHM 654 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGHKIE
BETA-COV-HKU24 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGHKIE
MURINE-HEP-17 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGHKIE
HUMAN-COV-OC43 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGHKIE
MURINE-HEP-VIRU 654 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGHKIE
RABBIT-COV-HKU1 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGNKIE
BOVINE-COV-98LU 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGNKIE
BOVINE-COV-98EN 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGNKIE
MURINE-COV-JHM 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGHKIE
BOVINE-COV-BEC 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGNKIE
BOVINE-COV-MEBU 649 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGNKIE
BOVINE-COV-Alpa 567 NECAQVLSEIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAFANSVFNICQAVSANVCSLMACNGNKIE
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU 648 NECAQVLSEVALSNGGLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSFANLNFQATAANVAQLLATPTSRIY
BEL-WHALE-COV_S 648 NECAQVLSEVALSNGGLYVKPGGTS **SGDAT**TAYANSFANLNFQATAANVAQLLATPTSRIY
BAT-COV-512_200 647 NELAQVLTEMVYSNGGFYVKPGGTT **SGDAT**TAYANSVFNIFQATSANVNRLLSVDSNTCN

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	717	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDTFVNEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCFNSTYASQGLV
SARS-COV	717	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDHEFVDEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCYNSNYAAQGLV
SARS-COV-PUMC02	717	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDHEFVDEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCYNSNYAAQGLV
BetaCoV_JL2012	717	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDHEFVDEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCYNSNYAAQGLV
BAT-COV	717	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDHEFVDEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCYNSNYAAQGLV
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	717	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDHEFVDEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCYNSNYAAQGLV
BtRf-BETACOV_He	717	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDHEFVDEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCYNSNYAAQGLV
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	717	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDHEFVGEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCYNSNYAAQGLV
BAT-COV-HKU3	717	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDHEFVDEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCYNSNYAAQGLV
BAT-COV-279_200	717	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDHEFVDEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCYNSNYAAQGLV
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	640	DKYVRNLQHRLYECLYRNRDVDHEFVDEFYAYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDAVVCYNSNYAAQGLV
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	712	DVYIRDLQRKLYANVYRSVHVDFKVFDEYYAFLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVCYNSDYAVARGYI
BAT-COV-HKU9	714	TTYVQELQRRLYLGIYRSNTVDNELVLDYYNYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNADYAQKGYV
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	717	NSYVQGLQRRLYLGIYRTHTVDMELVTEYYNYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYV
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	714	TTYVQELQRRLYLGIYRSNTVDNELVLDYYNYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNADYAQKGYV
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	717	TTYVQDLQRRLYLGIYRSNTVDYELVLDYYNYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYAQAQKGYV
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	717	TTYVQDLQRRLYLGIYRSNTVDYELVLDYYNYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYAQAQKGYV
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	712	TTYVQELQRRLYMGYIYRSNTVDNELVLDYYNYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYAQAQKGYV
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	712	TTYVQELQRRLYMGYIYRSNTVDNELVLDYYNYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYAQAQKGYV
BETACOV-ERINACE	715	DKEVKDMQFELYVNVYRNSKPDFKFDVDRYYAFLNRHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNKYAARGYI
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	715	DKEVKDMQFELYVNVYRKSQDPKFDVDRYYAFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYATKGYI
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	715	DKEIRDMQFDLYVNVYRRNMPDQKFDVDRYYAFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYAQAQKGYV
BAT-COV-HKU5	717	DEEVKDMQFELYVNVYRKSQDPKFDVDRYYAFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYATKGYI
MERS-COV	714	DKEVKDMQFDLYVNVYRSTSPDKFDVDRYYAFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYAQAQKGYI
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	715	DREIKDMQFDLYINVYRKVVPDPKFDVDRYYAFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYAQAQKGYV
MERS-COV-ISK_20	714	DKEVKDMQFDLYVNVYRSTSPDKFDVDRYYAFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYAQAQKGYI
BAT-COV-133_200	715	DREIKDMQFDLYINVYRKVVPDPKFDVDRYYAFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYAQAQKGYV
MURINE-COV	709	DLSIRELQKRLYSNVYRADHVDPAFVNEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSEFASKGYI
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	709	DLSIRNLQKRLYSNVYRTDYVDYTFVNEYYEFLCKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYI
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	709	DLSIRNLQKRLYSNVYRTDYVDYTFVNEYYEFLCKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYI
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	711	DLSIRNLQKRLYSNVYRTDYVDYTFVNEYYEFLCKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYI
MURINE-COV-A59	709	DLSIRELQKRLYSNVYRADHVDPAFVSEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSEFASKGYI
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	709	DLSIRNLQKRLYSNVYRTDYVDYTFVNEYYEFLCKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYANKGYI
RAT-COV	709	DLSIRELQKRLYSNVYRADHVDPAFVSEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSEFASKGYI
MURINE-COV-RJHM	714	DLSIRELQKRLYSNVYRADHVDPAFVSEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSEFASKGYI
BETA-COV-HKU24	709	DLSIRSLQRRLYSHVYRSYVDPAFVNEFYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSEYASKGYI
MURINE-HEP-17	709	DLSIRELQKRLYSNVYRADHVDPAFVSEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSEFASKGYI
HUMAN-COV-OC43	709	DLSIRALQKRLYSHVYRSYVDPAFVTEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYI
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	714	DLSIRELQKRLYSNVYRADHVDPAFVSEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSEFASKGYI
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	709	DLSIRALQKRLYSHVYRSYVDPFVTEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYI
BOVINE-COV-98LU	709	DLSIRALQKRLYSHVYRSDMVDSTFVTEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYI
BOVINE-COV-98EN	709	DLSIRALQKRLYSHVYRSDMVDSTFVTEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYI
MURINE-COV-JHM	709	DLSIRELQKRLYSNVYRADHVDPAFVSEYYEFLNKHFSSMIIL	SDDGVVCYNSEFASKGYI
BOVINE-COV-BEC	709	DLSIRALQKRLYSHVYRSDMVDSTFVTEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYI
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	709	DLSIRALQKRLYSHVYRSDMVDSTFVTEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYI
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	627	DLSIRALQKRLYSHVYRSDMVDSTFVTEYYEFLNKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYI
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	708	VEEVRALQHELYTQVYRRDKPDMDFVYTFYAYLNKHFSLMIL	SDDGVVCYNKSYAEAGMV
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	708	AAEVRALQHELYTQVYRRDKPDMDFVYTFYAYLNKHFSLMIL	SDDGVVCYNKSYAEAGMV
BAT-COV-512_200	707	NIEVKQLQRKLYDCCYRSSVDQSFVEEYFGYLRKHFSSMMIL	SDDGVVCYNSEYAALGYV

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	777	ASIKNFKSVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
SARS-COV	777	ASIKNFKAVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
SARS-COV-PUMC02	777	ASIKNFKAVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
BetaCoV_JL2012	777	ASIKNFKAVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV	777	ASIKNFKAVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	777	ASIKNFKAVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
BtRf-BETACOV_He	777	ASIKNFKAVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	777	ASIKNFKAVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-HKU3	777	ASIKNFKAVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTRGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-279_200	777	ASIKNFKAVHYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	700	ASIKNFKAVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWTETDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKQGDDYVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	772	AGIKDFKQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVEHNGEQVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-HKU9	774	ADIQGFKELLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVDMKGEQVYLPYPDPSR
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	777	ADIQGFKELLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVDMHGEQVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	774	ADIQGFKELLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVDMKGEQVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	777	ADIQGFKELLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVDMKGEQVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	777	ADIQGFKELLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVDMKGEQVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	772	ADIQGFKELLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVDMKGEQVYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	772	ADIQGFKELLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVDMKGEQVYLPYPDPSR
BETACOV-ERINACE	775	AGIQNFKETLYYQNNVFLSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTLLIKEGEDHYFLYPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	775	ASIQNFKETLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTLFIKDGDDGYFLYPYPDPSR
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	775	ASIQNFKETLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTLFIKDGDDGYFLYPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-HKU5	777	ASIQNFKETLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTLFIKDGDDGYFLYPYPDPSR
MERS-COV	774	AGIQNFKETLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTLYIKDGDDGYFLYPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	775	ASIQNFKETLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTLYIKDGDDGYFLYPYPDPSR
MERS-COV-ISK_20	774	AGIQNFKETLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTLYIKDGDDGYFLYPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-133_200	775	ASIQNFKETLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTLYIKDGDDGYFLYPYPDPSR
MURINE-COV	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	769	ANISVFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	769	ANISVFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	771	ANISVFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
MURINE-COV-A59	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
RAT-COV	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
MURINE-COV-RJHM	774	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
BETA-COV-HKU24	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
MURINE-HEP-17	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
HUMAN-COV-OC43	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	774	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
BOVINE-COV-98LU	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
BOVINE-COV-98EN	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
MURINE-COV-JHM	769	ANISDFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
BOVINE-COV-BEC	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	769	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	687	ANISAFQQVLYYQNNVFMSEAKCWVEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDEVYLPYPDPSR
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	768	ASIASFREVLFYQNNVFMADSKCWTEEDVKIGPHEFCSQHSMLVEIDGEMRYLPYPDPSR
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	768	ASIASFREVLFYQNNVFMADSKCWTEEDVKIGPHEFCSQHSMLVEIDGEMRYLPYPDPSR
BAT-COV-512_200	767	ADLNAFKAVLYYQNNVFMASAKCWIEPDLTKGPHEFCSQHTMQIVDKDGTYYLPYPDPSR

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	837	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
SARS-COV	837	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
SARS-COV-PUMC02	837	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
BetaCoV_JL2012	837	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
BAT-COV	837	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	837	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
BtRf-BETACOV_He	837	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	837	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
BAT-COV-HKU3	837	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
BAT-COV-279_200	837	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	760	ILGAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHPNQEYADVFLYLYQYIRKLHDELT
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	832	ILGACCFVDDVVKTDGTLMIERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHENPEYKQVFFYLLLYQYIKKLHEELT
BAT-COV-HKU9	834	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDGTLMMERYVSLAIDAYPLTKHPDPEYQNVFWCYLYQYIKKLHEELT
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	837	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDGTLMMERYVSLAIDAYPLTKHHDPEYQNVFWCYLYQYIKKLHEELT
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	834	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDGTLMMERYVSLAIDAYPLTKHSDPEYQNVFWCYLYQYIKKLHEELT
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	837	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDGTLMMERYVSLAIDAYPLTKHSDPEYQNVFWCYLYQYIKKLHEELT
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	837	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDGTLMMERYVSLAIDAYPLTKHSDPEYQNVFWCYLYQYIKKLHEELT
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	832	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDGTLMMERYVSLAIDAYPLTKHSDPEYQNVFWCYLYQYIKKLHEELT
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	832	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDGTLMMERYVSLAIDAYPLTKHSDPEYQNVFWCYLYQYIKKLHEELT
BETACOV-ERINACE	835	ILSAGCFVDDI IKTDGTLMVERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHDNIEYQNVFVVYLYQYIEKLYKDLT
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	835	ILSAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMVERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHDDPEYQNVFVVYLYQYIEKLYKDLT
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	835	ILSAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMVERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHEDLEYQNVFVVYLYQYIEKLYKDLT
BAT-COV-HKU5	837	ILSAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMVERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHDDPEYQNVFVVYLYQYIEKLYKDLT
MERS-COV	834	ILSAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMVERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHEDIEYQNVFVVYLYQYIEKLYKDLT
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	835	ILSAGCFVDDIVKTDGTVMMERYVSLAIDAYPLTKHDDTEYQNVFVVYLYQYIEKLYKDLT
MERS-COV-ISK_20	834	ILSAGCFVDDIVKTDGTLMVERFVSLAIDAYPLTKHEDIEYQNVFVVYLYQYIEKLYKDLT
BAT-COV-133_200	835	ILSAGCFVDDIVKTDGTVMMERYVSLAIDAYPLTKHDDTEYQNVFVVYLYQYIEKLYKDLT
MURINE-COV	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	831	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
MURINE-COV-A59	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
RAT-COV	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
MURINE-COV-RJHM	834	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
BETA-COV-HKU24	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
MURINE-HEP-17	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
HUMAN-COV-OC43	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	834	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
BOVINE-COV-98LU	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
BOVINE-COV-98EN	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
MURINE-COV-JHM	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
BOVINE-COV-BEC	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNELG
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	829	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNELG
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	747	ILGAGCFVDDLLKTDVSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENPEYQNVFRVYLYQYIEKLYNDLG
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	828	ILGACVFVDDVEKTEPVVVMERYVALAIDAYPLIYHENEYQKVFYLLLYSIQTLYQRLS
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	828	ILGACVFVDDVEKTEPVVVMERYVALAIDAYPLIYHENEYQKVFYLLLYSIQTLYQRLS
BAT-COV-512_200	827	ILSAGVFVDDIVKTDVPVILLERYVSLAIDAYPLSKHDNPEYRRVFTVMLDVKHLYKTLN

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

SARS-COV-2	897	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTVLQ
SARS-COV	897	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTVLQ
SARS-COV-PUMC02	897	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTVLQ
BetaCoV_JL2012	897	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTILQ
BAT-COV	897	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTILQ
BAT-SARS-COV-Y7	897	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTVLQ
BtRf-BETACOV_He	897	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTILQ
BAT-COV-Rp3_200	897	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTVLQ
BAT-COV-HKU3	897	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTVLQ
BAT-COV-279_200	897	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTVLQ
BAT-COV-Rp_Shaa	820	GHMLDMYSVMLTNDNTSRYWEPEFYEAMYPHTVLQ
BAT-BETACOV_Zhe	892	GHLDMYSVMI SGD NAQRYWEEDFYEAMYTQSVTLQ
BAT-COV-HKU9	894	GHLLDTYSVMLASDNASKYWEVEFYENMYMESATLQ
ROUSETTUS-BAT-C	897	GHLLDTYSVMLASENAAKYWEVEFYENMYTESATLQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-4	894	GHLLDTYSVMLASDNASKYWEVDFYENMYMESATLQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	897	GHLLDTYSVMLASDNAAKYWEVDFYENMYMESATLQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-5-	897	GHLLDTYSVMLASDNAAKYWEVDFYENMYMESATLQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-10	892	GHLLDTYSVMLASDNASKYWEVDFYENMYMESATLQ
BAT-COV-HKU9-3	892	GHLLDTYSVMLASDNASKYWEVDFYENMYMESATLQ
BETACOV-ERINACE	895	GHMLDYSVMLCGDNSSKFWEEQFYKDLYSAPTTLQ
BAT-COV-HKU5-2	895	GHMLDSYSVMLCGDNSSAKFWEEESFYRDLYTAPTTLQ
BtVs-BetaCoV_SC	895	GHMLDSYSVMLCGDNSSAKFWEEESFYRELYEAPTTLQ
BAT-COV-HKU5	897	GHMLDSYSVMLCGDNSSAKFWEEESFYRDLYTAPTTLQ
MERS-COV	894	GHMLDSYSVMLCGDNSSAKFWEEAFYRDLYSSPTTLQ
BAT-COV-HKU4-2	895	GHMLDSYSVMLCGDSSAKFWEEGFYRDLYSSPTTLQ
MERS-COV-ISK_20	894	GHMLDSYSVMLCGDNSSAKFWEEAFYRDLYSSPTTLQ
BAT-COV-133_200	895	GHMLDSYSVMLCGDSSAKFWEEGFYRDLYSSPTTLQ
MURINE-COV	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDETFYKNMYLRSAVMQ
HUMAN-COV-HKU1-	889	TQILDSYSVILSTCDGLKFTTEESFYKNMYLKSAVMQ
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	889	TQILDSYSVILSTCDGLKFTDES FYKNMYLKSAVMQ
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	891	TQILDSYSVILSTCDGLKFTTEESFYKNMYLKSAVMQ
MURINE-COV-A59	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDETFYKNMYLRSAVLQ
HUMAN-COV-HKU1_	889	TQILDSYSVILSTCDGLKFTTEESFYKNMYLKSAVMQ
RAT-COV	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDETFYKNMYLRSAVMQ
MURINE-COV-RJHM	894	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDETFYKNMYLRSAVMQ
BETA-COV-HKU24	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDES FYKNMYLRSAVMQ
MURINE-HEP-17	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDETFYKNMYLRSAVMQ
HUMAN-COV-OC43	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDES FYKNMYLRSAVMQ
MURINE-HEP-VIRU	894	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDETFYKNMYLRSAVLQ
RABBIT-COV-HKU1	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDES FYKNMYLRSAVMQ
BOVINE-COV-98LU	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDES FYKNMYLRSAVMQ
BOVINE-COV-98EN	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDES FYKNMYLRSAVMQ
MURINE-COV-JHM	889	NQILDSISVILSTCDGQKFTDETFYKNMYLRSAVMQ
BOVINE-COV-BEC	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDES FYKNMYLRSAVMQ
BOVINE-COV-MEBU	889	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDES FYKNMYLRSAVMQ
BOVINE-COV-Alpa	807	NQILDSYSVILSTCDGQKFTDES FYKNMYLRSAVMQ
BOT-DOLPHIN-HKU	888	NDMLMDYSFVMNIDTSSKFWEEEDFYRQMYESSPTLQ
BEL-WHALE-COV_S	888	NDMLMDYSFVMNIDTSSKFWEEEDFYRQMYGSSPTLQ
BAT-COV-512_200	887	QGVLDSFSVTLLEDATAKFWDES FYASMYEQSSVLQ

Figura Suplementaria 2. Continuación.

>Mpro_SARS-CoV-2

AGTGGTTTTAGAAAAATGGCATTCCCATCTGGTAAAGTTGAGGGTTGTATGGTACAAGTAACTT
GTGGTACAACACTACTTAACGGTCTTTGGCTTGATGACGTAGTTTACTGTCCAAGACATGTGATC
TGCACCTCTGAAGACATGCTTAACCCTAATTATGAAGATTTACTCATTTCGTAAGTCTAATCATAA
TTTCTTGGTACAGGCTGGTAATGTTCAACTCAGGGTTATTGGACATTCTATGCAAAATTGTGTAC
TTAAGCTTAAGGTTGATACAGCCAATCCTAAGACACCTAAGTATAAGTTTGTTTCGCATTCAACCA
GGACAGACTTTTTTCAGTGTTAGCTTGTTACAATGGTTCACCATCTGGTGTTTACCAATGTGCTAT
GAGGCCCAATTTCACTATTAAGGGTTCATTCCTAATGGTTCATGTGGTAGTGTGGTTTTAACAA
TAGATTATGACTGTGTCTCTTTTTGTTACATGCACCATATGGAATTACCAACTGGAGTTCATGCT
GGCACAGACTTAGAAGGTAACCTTTTATGGACCTTTTGTGACAGGCAAACAGCACAAGCAGCTG
GTACGGACACAACACTATTACAGTTAATGTTTTAGCTTGGTTGTACGCTGCTGTTATAAATGGAGAC
AGGTGGTTTCTCAATCGATTTACCACAACCTCTTAATGACTTTAACCTTGTGGCTATGAAGTACAA
TTATGAACCTCTAACACAAGACCATGTTGACATACTAGGACCTCTTCTGCTCAAACCTGGAATTG
CCGTTTTAGATATGTGTGCTTCATTAAGAATTACTGCAAAATGGTATGAATGGACGTACCATA
TTGGGTAGTGCTTTATTAGAAGATGAATTTACACCTTTTGATGTTGTTAGACAATGCTCAGGTGT
TACTTTCCAA

Figura Suplementaria 3. Secuencia de cDNA de Mpro del SARS-CoV-2